

Grant Agreement N°: 101076765

D2.2 Online Training Materials

Co-funded by
the European Union

Document information Table

Project Data			
Project Acronym	BECKON		
Project Title	Boosting Energy Communities massive deployment by equipping local authorities with comprehensive technical assistance Cookbook, integrated services and capacity building		
Grant Agreement n.	101076765		
Topic identifier	LIFE-2021-CET-ENERCOM		
Project duration	36 months		
Coordinator	R2M Solution SL		
Deliverable Document Sheet			
Deliverable No.	D2.2		
Deliverable title	Online Training Materials		
Description	This deliverable is a report collecting all the online training materials that will be available through the LIFE-BECKON one stop shop Knowledge and Training Hub.		
WORK PACKAGE No.	2		
Lead beneficiary	ENoLL		
Author(s) & contributor(s)	Authors: Marta De Los Rios White (ENoLL), Elina Makousiari (ENoLL) Contributors: Davide Bastolla (ENoLL), Aki Korpela (TAMK), Aki Kortemaki (TAMK)		
Type	R – Document, report		
Dissemination L.	PU - Public		
Due Date	October 2023 (original) January 2024 (amended) January 2026 (amended)	Submission Date	30 January 2026

Version	Date	Author(s)	Organisation	Comments
V0	18 January 2024	Marta De Los Ríos White Elina Makousiari	ENoLL ENoLL	Complete draft for internal review
V1	26 January 2024	Aki Korpela Nadya Nikolova Francesco Milani	TAMK SOFENA R2M	Quality review from partners
V2	28 January 2024	Giulia Campodonico	ENoLL	Internal independent quality review
V3	30 January 2024	Marta De Los Ríos White Elina Makousiari	ENoLL ENoLL	Final version of deliverable ready for submission
V4	22 January 2026	Marta De Los Rios White	ENoLL	Update of information regarding the LIFE-BECKON OneStopShop

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Abbreviation list

D	Deliverable
ENoLL	European Network of Living Labs
GA	Grant Agreement
LIFE	Programme for Environment and Climate Action
LL	Living Lab
LLIP	Living Lab Integrative Process
OIJ	Open Innovation Journey
OSS	One-Stop-Shop
REC	Renewable Energy Communities
TAMK	Tampere University of Applied Sciences
TAO	Technical Assistance Office

Executive Summary

The LIFE-BECKON project is dedicated to expediting the establishment of Energy Communities across Europe, providing vital support for public authorities, promoters, and Local Action Groups. Through innovative mechanisms, like a Technical Assistance Cookbook, a “Train the Trainers” Capacity Building Programme, and an integrated One-Stop-Shop (OSS) Platform¹, the project aims to empower stakeholders in Ávila (Spain), Sofia (Bulgaria), and Copenhagen (Denmark). Led by the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL), LIFE-BECKON employs a “Train the Trainers” approach, focusing on Open Innovation and Living Lab methodologies to empower local stakeholders.

This deliverable presents a comprehensive report on the online training materials systematically organized in alignment with insights from previous deliverables. It provides a condensed summary of the video development process, outlines the methodological approach, themes covered, integration of the Open Innovation Journeys (OIJ) methodology, and accessibility aspects within the LIFE- BECKON OSS Platform. The document concludes with next steps, emphasizing continuous improvement and user engagement for ongoing enhancement of training materials.

Importance and relevance of the training materials to Energy Communities

Aligned with the objectives outlined in the Grant Agreement (GA), the collaborative and tailored approach signifies a commitment to fulfilling the GA's objectives effectively, ensuring stakeholders across diverse demonstrations and linguistic backgrounds can access valuable insights. By addressing specific needs identified through a comprehensive needs assessment detailed in the Public Deliverable (D)2.1 “Open Innovation Journeys”, the materials offer a practical and comprehensive resource for stakeholders involved in Energy Communities' development, including public authorities, energy agencies, and municipalities. The strategic development of video materials, deeply rooted in insights and aligned with the findings of the needs assessment, reflects a commitment to providing practical and tailored support for the diverse challenges faced by stakeholders, enhancing the accessibility and applicability of the training materials.

The significance of the Open OIJ methodology is pivotal to LIFE-BECKON's comprehensive Capacity Building Programme. Developed by ENoLL, this methodology serves as a strategic guide for municipalities venturing into the creation of Energy Communities. More than a theoretical framework, the OIJ methodology becomes a practical tool through collaborative workshops, empowering municipal teams to facilitate user-centric sessions and draft implementation plans. Its adaptability and applicability to diverse contexts, emphasizing user engagement and co-creation, make it a catalyst for unlocking the full potential of Energy Communities. The OIJ methodology guides municipalities not only in the initial setup of Energy Communities but also equips them with tools and insights for long-term sustainability and success in fostering user acceptance for new products, services, or processes.

Approach for crafting the training materials

The methodological approach designed to embed the training materials within the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform's Training Hub is strategically designed to address the identified capacity building needs outlined in D2.1 “Open Innovation Journeys”. These materials, aimed at diverse stakeholders involved in Energy Communities, systematically provide insights, tools, and resources, emphasizing user engagement principles for active participation. The training materials consist of eight thematic videos and accompanying written materials in the form of slide decks, also accessible on the LIFE-BECKON OSS

¹ [LIFE-BECKON One-Stop-Shop \(OSS\) Platform](#)

Platform's Training Hub. Tailored for accessibility, the content uses simple language and targets a broad audience, including municipalities, ministries, public authorities, energy agencies, companies, associations, investors, developers, consultants, and citizens.

In the production of the eight training videos, a deliberate strategy focuses on optimizing engagement through concise yet comprehensive short-form videos, complemented by written materials. The videos cover various themes related to the identified capacity building needs. As proposed in the GA, a multilingual approach, with subtitles in eight European languages, namely Bulgarian, Danish, English, French, Finnish, German, Italian, and Spanish, ensures widespread accessibility.

The workflow involves meticulous content creation, scripting, professional voice-over recording, dynamic video production, and multilingual adaptation for accessibility.

The topics covered include the definition and benefits of Energy Communities, overcoming barriers, stakeholder engagement, governance models and legal structures, regulation highlights, financing and public aids, technical and technological considerations, and the operation of Energy Communities. Complementary written materials enhance understanding, offering in-depth insights and resources. The videos aim to engage a broad audience and contribute to the successful establishment and support of Energy Communities, promoting sustainability and community-driven energy initiatives.

For the OIJ methodology, detailed in D2.1, it serves as a user-friendly guide for municipalities in establishing or supporting Energy Communities. Comprising seven major steps, each with guiding questions, the OIJ methodology emphasizes collaboration, co-creation, and user-centricity. To enhance practical application, the methodology is converted into a user-friendly tool accessible on the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform's Training Hub upon free registration. The modular approach allows users to select specific tools tailored to their co-creation needs for Energy Communities. Developed by ENOLL, the OIJ methodology draws from scientific theories on open innovation and Living Lab literature, ensuring valuable insights and guidance for municipalities.

The LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform Training Hub, developed by Work Package 3 “Integrated services through One-Stop-Shop Platform”, prioritizes optimal accessibility and a seamless user experience. Built on a user-

centric design, it will integrate training materials into a unified and user-friendly space, featuring videos, tools, OIJ methodology, and written materials. Thematic videos offer tailored, multilingual experiences, complemented by downloadable slide decks and an interactive "Comments" section for user engagement. The OIJ is strategically integrated, unfolding systematically through downloadable templates. Going beyond a traditional repository, the Training Hub transforms into an interactive space with features like an "Ideas" section and a proposed "Forum," creating a dynamic learning environment that empowers stakeholders in comprehending and contributing to Energy Communities.

Training materials from the LIFE-BECKON Cookbook and Sister Projects

The LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform's Training Hub will host valuable additional materials, enhancing its comprehensive offerings. A central component is the LIFE-BECKON Technical Assistance Cookbook, a guide for public authorities and promoters in Energy Community development, which is currently being developed by Work Package 1 "Comprehensive Cookbook for technical assistance". Covering technical, financial, regulatory, and participatory dimensions, the Cookbook incorporates self-assessment checklists and emphasizes participatory processes. Integrated into the platform's architecture, it bridges the Guidance Hub and Training Hub, providing practical tools seamlessly.

Beyond the Cookbook, we spotlight the collaborative efforts of European initiatives under the topic "Developing support mechanisms for Energy Communities and other citizen-led initiatives in the field of sustainable energy" (LIFE21-CET-ENERCOM) - often referred to as LIFE sister projects - aligned with the theme of sustainable energy initiatives. United under the LIFE21-CET-ENERCOM topic, these projects will contribute diverse resources to the platform.

Additionally, the Platform will feature contributions from projects under the LIFE21-CET-ENERCOM² initiative - often referred to as LIFE sister projects. These projects align with sustainable energy goals and will enrich the Platform with diverse resources. Collaborative efforts among sister projects, facilitated by LIFE-LOOP³, aim to curate a cohesive collection of Capacity Building resources. The collaborative approach will ensure a broad spectrum of insights and expertise to support sustainable Energy Communities, contributing to the collective knowledge-sharing environment provided by the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform.

LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform Training Hub as a collaborative ecosystem

In conclusion, the LIFE-BECKON project stands at the forefront of empowering communities for sustainable energy initiatives, bridging the gap between innovation, education, and practical implementation. As we embark on this transformative journey, the commitment to continuous improvement and user engagement remains steadfast, ensuring that our training materials evolve in tandem with the dynamic landscape of Energy Communities.

The envisaged Training Hub within the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform is not merely a repository but a vibrant ecosystem, fostering collaboration, idea-sharing, and collective growth. By integrating valuable resources such as the Technical Assistance Cookbook and contributions from LIFE sister projects, we strive to create a comprehensive knowledge-sharing environment that caters to the diverse needs of stakeholders, including the cities who will act as replicators and will be supported by Work Package 5 "Mass-replication, exploitation, dissemination and communication".

² [LIFE-2021-CET-ENERCOM Developing support mechanisms for energy communities and other citizen-led initiatives in the field of sustainable energy.](#)

³ [LIFE-LOOP project](#)

As the LIFE-BECKON project advances, its continued emphasis is on the empowerment of communities, the advocacy for sustainable practices, and alignment with the overarching goals of the European Union. Active participation from diverse stakeholders, including public authorities and citizens, is encouraged to collectively contribute to this joint initiative. The aim is to shape a future where Energy Communities not only prosper but also drive innovation, playing a pivotal role in steering towards a more sustainable and resilient energy landscape in accordance with the project's objectives.

1. Introduction

The LIFE-BECKON project aims to accelerate the establishment of Energy Communities throughout Europe. It strives to provide comprehensive support mechanisms for public authorities, promoters, and Local Action Groups. These mechanisms include a Technical Assistance Cookbook for creating Technical Assistance Offices, a Capacity Building Programme using a “Train the Trainers” approach, and an integrated One-Stop-Shop platform offering information, tools, and guides, as well as matchmaking services. The project will be validated in three diverse supramunicipal areas: Ávila (Spain), Sofia (Bulgaria), and Copenhagen (Denmark). The consortium, consisting of eight partners from seven European countries, covers various expertise areas and is committed to launching and validating solutions in specific geographical areas.

Led by the European Network of Living Labs (ENoLL), LIFE-BECKON adopts a "Train the Trainers" approach for knowledge sharing and capacity building. This approach to capacity building involves training individuals who, in turn, become trainers themselves. Instead of directly training the end-users or participants, the focus is on empowering individuals with the necessary knowledge and skills to train others. This method is often employed in professional development, educational programmes, and various initiatives where the goal is to disseminate specific expertise widely.

This strategy targets public authorities at various levels, regional energy agencies, municipalities, ministries, Local Action Groups, associations, and energy companies working on Energy Communities. The project focuses on Open Innovation and Living Labs methodologies to empower local stakeholders.

The purpose of this deliverable is to compile a comprehensive report consolidating all online training materials accessible through the LIFE-BECKON One-Stop-Shop (OSS) Platform⁴, specifically via the Training Hub. Developed collaboratively, in alignment with the insights outlined in Deliverable (D)2.1 "Open Innovation Journeys," these materials aim to furnish stakeholders, including public authorities, energy agencies, municipalities, and other contributors to Energy Communities development, with a systematically organized repository of training resources. This compilation adheres to the “Train the Trainers” approach and integrates the findings of the needs assessment presented in D2.1 and summarised in Figure 1, thereby ensuring relevance and effectiveness in addressing identified requirements.

Emphasizing the significance of these materials, we offer a condensed summary of the video development process, linking it to D2.1 “Open Innovation Journeys”. Highlighting the centrality of these materials to our Capacity Building Programme, we address specific needs identified through a needs assessment and core topics, concluding with the broader value they bring to the context of Energy Communities in Section 2.

While this deliverable focuses on the online training materials developed, the upcoming D2.3 “Report on the Capacity Building Programme” due in April 2024 will present all activities performed as part of Work Package 2 “Capacity Building via “Train the Trainers”.

Figure 1. Summary of thematic areas identified in D2.1.

⁴ [LIFE-BECKON One-Stop-Shop \(OSS\) Platform](#)

The methodological approach applied in crafting the online training materials is explored in Section 3. This includes insights into design choices, such as optimal video duration and the complementary nature of slide decks. Additionally, we provide details on the meticulous process of video creation, explaining strategic avoidance of repetition and integration of insights from other projects for cross-fertilization. The target audience is defined, emphasizing simplicity and generality in language. The translation process and provision of materials in multiple languages are outlined, and the objectives of the slide decks prepared as part of additional materials in the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform are outlined.

Themes and specific topics covered by the videos are detailed in Section 4. Categorizing the materials into themes, we offer clarity on sub-topics covered by each video and its corresponding slide deck, providing users with a comprehensive guide to navigate content relevant to their interests within the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform.

The integration of the OIJ methodology within the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform is explained in Section 5, detailing how users can access and leverage it for their benefit. Clear instructions are provided to enhance user understanding and utilization of this valuable resource.

Furthermore, in Section 5, the deliverable includes information about resources from the Cookbook and LIFE sister projects, ensuring a holistic approach to capacity building. These additional resources, relevant to the objectives of the LIFE-BECKON project, will also be made available through the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform. By consolidating materials from both LIFE-BECKON and related sister projects, the deliverable facilitates a comprehensive and collaborative knowledge-sharing environment to support the replication and dissemination of best practices within the European community. The inclusion of sister project resources enhances the richness and diversity of training materials accessible to stakeholders.

The accessibility and user experience aspects of the materials within the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform are elaborated upon in Section 6. Serving as a guide, we offer insights into how users will be able to navigate the platform and access the training materials seamlessly.

In the concluding segment, next steps are outlined, focusing on continuous improvement and feedback mechanisms. We underscore the importance of user engagement through forums and comments fields within the platform, encouraging users to share their feedback. Recommendations for avoiding common mistakes and focusing on specific aspects are provided, ensuring a user-centric approach for ongoing enhancement of the materials.

2. Importance and relevance of the materials to Energy Communities

Aligned with the objectives outlined in the Grant Agreement (GA), the development of the Open Innovation Journey (OIJ) methodology and capacity building videos within the LIFE-BECKON project follows a structured and collaborative approach. The emphasis on co-creation elements is pivotal, extending beyond theoretical knowledge to practical application at the community level. This approach aims to foster collaboration across diverse sectors, engaging citizens, and stakeholders actively in the development of Energy Communities. The commitment to promoting mutual learning and knowledge exchange is a core principle of this training initiative.

Under the coordination of ENoLL, the European Network of Living Labs, the development and collection of educational materials are executed with meticulous planning. These materials are crafted to facilitate mutual learning among the partner demonstrations. They are made available through the Training Hub in the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform upon free registration.

As proposed in the Grant Agreement (GA) the specific format for these educational materials includes eight video lessons in English, ensuring a standardized and accessible medium for knowledge dissemination. In addition to the videos, a series of written materials are prepared, translated into eight European languages. This multilingual approach is not only in compliance with the GA's stipulations but also aligns with the project's commitment to inclusivity and widespread accessibility. Section 3.1 details the methodological approach followed to develop the videos.

By adhering to the outlined strategy, the LIFE-BECKON project strives to fulfil the GA's objectives effectively. The collaborative training and development activities, coupled with the creation of tailored educational materials, signify a holistic approach toward capacity building. This approach ensures that stakeholders across different demonstrations and linguistic backgrounds can access valuable insights, fostering a harmonized and collective effort towards the successful establishment and development of Energy Communities.

2.1. Core of Capacity Building: Addressing Needs through Needs Assessment and Core Topics

The development of our training materials for the Capacity Building Programme is intricately linked to the insights presented in D2.1 "Open Innovation Journeys", as a pivotal reference point. This deliverable has been instrumental in structuring our content and tailoring it to meet the identified needs of Energy Communities.

Through a meticulous process, including internal workshops, multilingual surveys (English, Spanish, Danish, and Bulgarian), and targeted interviews with LIFE-BECKON demo cities, ENoLL conducted an exhaustive needs assessment. The overview of the results obtained are shown in Figure 2. This inclusive consultation process enabled us to discern the specific requirements and challenges faced by stakeholders involved in Energy Communities development.

Figure 2. Overview of the results of the needs assessment identification for the LIFE-BECKON Capacity Building Programme.

The thematic areas identified as critical for Capacity Building in D2.1 - namely Technical Issues, Stakeholder Engagement, Governance and Business Models Set-Up Processes, Best Practices/Examples from Successful Energy Communities, and Legal and Regulatory Processes - formed the guiding principles for our Capacity Building Programme. These topics were systematically integrated into the video materials, ensuring a direct link between the identified needs and the core content of our training resources. Additionally, these findings align seamlessly with the core thematic areas identified in the LIFE-BECKON proposal stage, emphasizing their critical relevance in shaping our Capacity Building Programme.

The highlighted topics have emerged as essential facets for the successful development and deployment of Energy Communities. While the six main themes were prioritized, other significant areas like management and administration, assessment and monitoring were also considered, ensuring a comprehensive approach in our materials.

Our belief in the value of these materials for Energy Communities lies in their ability to provide targeted, accessible, and user-friendly knowledge dissemination. By encapsulating the identified needs and core topics, our training materials offer a practical and comprehensive resource for stakeholders, including public authorities, energy agencies, and municipalities. The aim is not only to equip these stakeholders with the essential knowledge but also to empower them to navigate the intricacies of establishing and sustaining Energy Communities.

In essence, the strategic development of video materials, deeply rooted in the insights from D2.1 and aligned with the findings of our needs assessment, reflects our commitment to providing practical and tailored support for the diverse challenges faced by stakeholders in the realm of Energy Communities. This approach not only enhances the accessibility and applicability of the training materials but also underscores their inherent value as a key driver for the success and sustainability of Energy Communities across Europe.

2.2. Unlocking Energy Community Potential: The Significance of Open Innovation Journeys

The OIJ methodology is pivotal to LIFE-BECKON's comprehensive Capacity Building Programme, serving as a strategic guide for municipalities embarking on the creation of Energy Communities. Developed by ENoLL, tested by TAMK, the Tampere University of Applied Sciences, and subsequently validated through on-site workshops in the demo sites, this innovative methodology ensures a robust approach to community development. By providing a structured journey comprising seven essential steps, the OIJ methodology becomes a practical tool for municipalities, fostering user-centricity, collaboration, and sustainable practices. The detailed steps of the methodology are available in D2.1 "Open Innovation Journey".

Unlocking the potential of Energy Communities, the OIJ methodology integrates the principles of Open Innovation and Living Labs (LL). Its role extends beyond theoretical concepts to tangible, hands-on applications. Through collaborative workshops, trainers from ENoLL empower municipal teams, enabling them to facilitate user-centric sessions, validate assumptions, and draft implementation plans. The OIJ methodology, becomes an actionable blueprint for municipalities, ensuring not only the establishment but also the sustainable growth of Energy Communities.

The significance of the OIJ methodology lies in its adaptability and applicability to diverse contexts. By emphasizing user engagement and co-creation, it addresses the unique needs and expectations of different communities, ensuring the inclusivity and success of Energy Communities across Europe. As demonstrated in the detailed steps outlined in D2.1, the OIJ methodology is more than a theoretical framework: it is a practical tool that municipalities can leverage to navigate the complexities of community development, reduce failure rates, and foster user acceptance for new products, services, or processes.

The OIJ methodology, embedded in the LIFE-BECKON project, becomes a catalyst for unlocking the full potential of Energy Communities. Through its tested and validated approach, it not only guides municipalities in their initial setup but also equips them with the tools and insights needed for long-term sustainability and success.

3. Methodological approach

The methodological approach employed in crafting the training materials for the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform's Training Hub is rooted in a deliberate strategy addressing the identified capacity building needs outlined in D2.1. These materials aim to explore specific requirements and challenges faced by diverse stakeholders, systematically providing insights, tools, and resources for further exploration. Focusing on user-centric principles, the training materials emphasise user engagement, aiming to empower and educate users to actively participate in Energy Community initiatives.

The training materials encompass a series of eight thematic videos covering different aspects of Energy Communities and the OIJ methodology in a downloadable format suitable for various Energy Community contexts. All materials will be accessible on the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform and its Training Hub upon free registration.

Tailored for accessibility, we deliberately utilized simple and generic language to ensure that the content of both the training videos and OIJ is easily comprehensible for a wide range of stakeholders, catering to both newcomers and those experienced in Energy Communities. The target audience for these training materials is extensive, including Municipalities, Ministries, Public Authorities, energy agencies, companies, associations, investors, developers, consultants, and citizens. This intentional inclusivity aims to make the materials not only informative but also relevant and engaging across the Energy Communities landscape.

The subsequent sections provide a detailed overview of the approach used to produce the training videos and the adaptation of the OIJ methodology from D2.1, transforming it into a co-creation tool for Energy Communities.

3.1. Training videos

The design rationale for the series of training videos centres around optimizing engagement without overwhelming the audience. The primary goal is to offer a collection of concise yet comprehensive short-form videos, carefully considering an optimal duration of approximately 3 to 4 minutes. This duration aims to maintain viewers' interest while delivering essential insights across the various themes covered. Each video is paired with complementary written materials in the form of slide decks available in .pdf format.

These written materials function as the primary resource for content creation in each video and are accessible in the Training Hub of the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform upon free registration. They serve to complement the videos, allowing for a more in-depth exploration of the addressed topics. Additionally, it is noteworthy that each video maintains a broader and more generic level of information upon the theme explored. For more in-depth insights, viewers are encouraged to register on the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform, where additional resources and references can be found. This integrated approach ensures a well-rounded and accessible learning experience, catering to diverse levels of interest and exploration.

We adopted a multilingual approach to meet the GA requirements and LIFE-BECKON's goal of inclusivity and broad accessibility. The videos will have subtitles in eight European languages, namely Bulgarian, Danish, German, French, Finnish, English, Italian, and Spanish, making them accessible to a wider audience. Written materials will also be available in these languages, ensuring everyone can access valuable resources.

Figure 3 below presents an overview of the structured workflow employed in the creation of training videos. The development process followed encompasses content creation through written materials,

creative scripting, professional voice-over recording, dynamic video production, and a commitment to accessibility through multilingual adaptation.

Figure 3. Workflow of training videos' production.

The development process commenced with the development of the written materials, primarily in the form of slide decks. These materials were developed by TAMK and aimed to serve as the foundation for the video content, covering the selected themes related to Energy Communities. The content produced by TAMK was thoroughly designed to align with the identified needs for capacity building, ensuring a comprehensive exploration of the identified issues and challenges. The written materials of all the videos went through multiple feedback loops with relevant project partners, to assure quality, preventing disseminating misinformation or inaccuracies, enrich the materials with a broader range of knowledge and insights, as well as safeguard accuracy and consistency among the produced materials and the work being done in relevant Work Packages of the project.

After the integration of the feedback received, all slide decks underwent a comprehensive editing phase led by ENoLL to ensure consistency and aesthetic coherence across topics. This meticulous editing involved refining the visual presentation of each slide, harmonizing design elements, and ensuring uniformity in formatting and layout. By standardizing the appearance of the slide decks, ENoLL aimed to enhance visual appeal and facilitate a seamless transition between different topics covered in the videos. This final touch not only elevates the overall professionalism of the materials but also contributes to a more cohesive and engaging learning experience for users across the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform.

Upon the completion of the written materials, the next step involved translating this content into creative and attractive video scripts. The scripting phase was coordinated by ENoLL, with collaborative efforts with the in-house video maker working on the video production, as well as the project partners that were again involved in multiple feedback loops. Our goal for the scripts was to transform the written materials into engaging and concise scripts that will serve as the backbone of the training videos.

The recording of the voice-over was followed, as a crucial step in bringing the scripts to life. Initially, a draft recording was produced, to help the next phase of visualising the video's flow and animation. Subsequently, a professional recording was done by ENoLL colleagues in a professional studio setting, ensuring high-quality audio that complemented the visual elements of the videos. Adding the high-quality of the videos' audio, a tailor-made production of the audio, including enhancement of the voice recording and identification of the most suitable music was done by a professional. Choosing a captivating and well-matched to the training videos music, contribute to maintaining a well-paced flow throughout the video, and, thus, enhancing viewers' engagement, and sustaining their attention.

The core phase of the videos' productions involved the conceptualisation and design of the visual elements that would best describe their content. When producing the animation of the training videos, it was essential to synchronize visual elements with the narrative based on the written materials, to avoid confusion and enhance viewers' understanding. ENoLL working closely with the professional in-house video maker, went through multiple iterations of the visual elements, making sure that the spoken and written content of each video in delivering a cohesive message.

Additionally, we aimed on creating engaging and informative videos that transcend language barriers and captivates the audience's attention throughout the learning experience. To do so, various sensitive visuals, including, inclusive, culturally diverse, and gender-balanced images and animations, as well simple and inclusive language was used in the animations, targeting to reach viewers from different linguistic and cultural backgrounds. Draft versions of the video went through multiple cycles of feedback from the project partners, to ensure alignment with the project objectives and the identified stakeholders needs. Beside the translation of the content to a captivating video animation, project partners provided valuable feedback as viewers as well, that further helped on making the video attractive and relevant for viewers.

To enhance accessibility, and according to the GA, the videos and complementary written materials were translated into eight European languages, namely Bulgarian, English, Danish, French, Finnish, German, Italian, and Spanish. This multilingual approach ensures that a diverse audience can engage with the content effectively. Additionally, subtitling in all the eight languages was employed to provide a comprehensive experience for viewers across different linguistic backgrounds. This deliverable presents the original video scripts and slide decks in English.

The translation process for the slide decks was a collaborative effort, leveraging both AI technology and human expertise to ensure accuracy and quality across all languages. Initially, the machine translation tool embedded in Canva⁵ was employed to generate translations in the seven European languages besides English specified. However, to guarantee linguistic precision and cultural relevance, these initial translations were meticulously reviewed and adapted by native or advanced speakers proficient in each language. These reviewers were drawn from both ENOLL and project partners, bringing a wealth of language proficiency and cultural insight to the task. Through this combined approach, the translated slide decks were refined to align seamlessly with the linguistic nuances and cultural contexts of each target audience, thereby enhancing accessibility and comprehension for users across diverse linguistic backgrounds.

Finally, the produced videos together with the complementary slide deck will be uploaded to the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform. Furthermore, the videos will be shared on ENOLL's YouTube channel, ensuring seamless sharing, and embedding across various platforms. The release schedule for these videos is detailed in Table 1. The release of a teaser video is scheduled on 1 February 2024, marking the beginning of the weekly video release plan.

Table 1. Video release schedule

Video	Date of release
Teaser	1 February 2024
Video 1: Definition and benefits of Energy Communities	8 February 2024
Video 2: Overcoming barriers in Energy Communities	15 February 2024
Video 3: Stakeholder engagement in Energy Communities	22 February 2024
Video 4: Governance models and legal structures for Energy Communities	29 February 2024
Video 5: Regulation highlights for Energy Communities	7 March 2024
Video 6: Financing of Energy Communities and Public Aids	14 March 2024
Video 7: Technical and technological considerations for Energy Communities	21 March 2024
Video 8: Operation of Energy Communities	28 March 2024

⁵ [Canva's AI Online Translator Tool](#)

3.2. Open Innovation Journey

The OIJ methodology, as detailed in D2.1 “Open Innovation Journeys”, serves as a comprehensive guide for municipalities in Europe seeking to establish Energy Communities or support their development. Grounded in the principles of open innovation and the Living Lab Integrative Approach (LLIP) developed by Mastelic, 2019⁶, this methodology emphasizes collaboration, co-creation, and user-centricity.

The OIJ methodology comprises seven major steps:

- **Step 1.** Purpose
- **Step 2.** SWOT Analysis
- **Step 3.** COCD Box
- **Step 4.** Stakeholder Mapping
- **Step 5.** Power Vs Interest Matrix
- **Step 6.** OIJ & Validation
- **Step 7.** Implementation Plan

Each step poses a set of pivotal questions designed to steer and facilitate thoughtful deliberation throughout the process. These steps provide a holistic journey, guiding contributors from setting or supporting Energy Communities’ purpose to drafting an implementation plan for delivering green solution packages and smart energy services.

Figure 4 below presents an overview of the OIJ steps, along with the guiding questions.

Figure 4. The main steps of the Open Innovation Journey (OIJ).

To enhance practical application, we strove to convert the OIJ methodology into a user-friendly tool, accessible on the Training Hub of the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform. This process aims to provide a

⁶ Mastelic, J. (2019). *Stakeholders’ engagement in the co-design of energy conservation interventions: The case of the Energy Living Lab*

straightforward and readily usable format for individuals and organizations interested in Energy Communities. Given that the methodology consists of a collection of tools, each step will be showcased independently through tool templates that can be downloaded by users. These templates will include explicit instructions and timing suggestions for practical implementation. Embracing a modular approach, this design allows users to select specific tools tailored to their unique co-creation needs for Energy Communities, with each tool serving as a standalone option.

The OIJ methodology, having been developed by ENoLL, draws from scientific theories on Open Innovation and LL literature. It is a culmination of years of research and practical experience in LL approaches, ensuring that it provides valuable insights and guidance for municipalities. For further details on the methodology and its application, interested individuals can refer to D2.1, which offers a comprehensive overview of the principles, steps, and tools involved in the OIJ. This deliverable will be available in the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform Training Hub upon free registration.

4. Themes and specific topics covered by the training videos

The series comprises eight thematic videos available in the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform, each delving into distinct aspects that are fundamental for establishing and/or supporting Energy Communities. Each video is thoroughly tailored to focus on a specific topic, offering valuable insights, practical tips, and diverse examples.

The videos aim to present an introductory overview of each addressed topic in an engaging and easily comprehensible manner. Complementing these videos, detailed written materials (slide decks) will also be available on the OSS Platform upon free registration, offering comprehensive elaboration and supplemental information corresponding to each video. These materials aim to enhance the understanding of the topics covered in the videos, providing in-depth insights and resources for further exploration.

- What is an Energy Community?
- What are the benefits of setting up an Energy Community?

- Insiders and outsiders in Energy Communities
- European Initiatives for inspiration and best practices
- Barriers to be taken into consideration when setting up Energy Communities

- What is a stakeholder?
- What is important to consider when engaging with stakeholders in Energy Communities?
- Communication strategies

- Why is governance important?
- Types of governance models
- Governance building principles

- EU regulatory framework
- Transposition of EU legislation into national level
- Tools to stay updated on EU regulation related to Energy Communities

- Funding from different authority levels for Energy Communities
- Forms of financing
- EU Public funds

- Technical and technological complexities when setting up Energy Communities
- Technical and technological considerations and smart energy transition in Energy Communities
- Energy Communities in the operational phase
- Monitoring and evaluation of Energy Communities
- Multidimensional maintenance for Energy Communities

Figure 5. Overview of themes and specific topics covered by the Capacity Building videos.

4.1. Video 1: Definition and benefits of Energy Communities

The first video of the series serves an introduction to Energy Communities. It presents the two primary types of Energy Communities: Renewable (REC) and Citizen Energy Communities (CEC), providing detailed definition of each type that describes their main characteristics. For each type, a comprehensive definition is provided, outlining their common and distinctive characteristics. The video further explores the differences between RECs and CECs,

covering aspects such as their geographic scope, participant profiles, the spectrum of activities, levels of autonomy, and decision-making authority. Additionally, it highlights the extensive array of benefits inherent in both Energy Community types, encompassing social, environmental, and economic benefits.

Complementary written materials parallel the video's content, offering in-depth coverage of Energy Community definitions, differences, and associated benefits. These materials include valuable resources and references to facilitate further exploration. The English script for Video 1 is provided below.

Box 1. Script of Video 1 on Definition and benefits of Energy Communities available in the Training Hub of the LIFE-BECKON One-Stop-Shop Platform.

Introduction

Welcome to the **vibrant world of Energy Communities**, a dynamic force driving the **smart energy transition**. These communities embody **innovation, sustainability, and shared prosperity** as they tackle today's most urgent environmental challenges.

What is an Energy Community?

An Energy Community is an **organization of individuals, families, or local entities** that collaborate to **produce, consume, and manage energy** in a **sustainable way**. There are two primary types of such communities: Renewable Energy Communities and Citizen Energy Communities. The first type

focuses on **sustainable energy generation and distribution** within a **specific geographical area**. These communities often come together to **harness renewable resources** like solar, wind, or hydro power. Citizen Energy Communities, on the other hand, are more diverse in their activities and can **extend beyond energy generation**.

They involve the **active participation of community members** in various energy-related projects. Both of these types are legal entities, and what makes them unique is their **emphasis on collaboration and community engagement**. They aim to empower individuals and local entities to **take control of their energy needs**, emphasizing **open and voluntary participation**. These two types of Energy Communities also have some differences, related to their **geographical scope**, the **range of activities** they undertake, the **participants** involved, the **level of autonomy** they possess, as well as their **effective control** over energy-related decisions.

Benefits of Energy Communities

Energy Communities also offer a wide range of benefits, driven not solely by financial profit, but by a commitment to a sustainable future overall. From the **economic perspective**, they contribute **reducing the costs** of the participants, **fostering entrepreneurship** and **economic development**, attracting **private investments**, stimulating **job creation**, and **generating revenue** for the local economy. There are also various environmental benefits that Energy Communities have to offer, including the **reduction of Greenhouse Gas emissions**, the **enhanced efficiency of energy use**, the **protection of the ecosystem** and the contribution overall to **sustainable development**, ensuring a **balance between environmental preservation and human well-being**.

But it does not stop there. Energy Communities have a profound impact on **society** as well. They can **empower communities** by involving citizens in local energy decisions, boost social cohesion, enhance people's capacity in energy management, offer **fair access to clean energy**, encourage **knowledge exchange**, as well as **raise awareness** on energy related matters.

Closing

Together, we can **reshape our energy landscape**, **drive sustainability**, and **enhance our communities**. Whether you're an individual, a family, or a local entity, you have the power to **make a difference** in your community and the world. Join the movement, fuel the change, and let's co-create a **brighter, cleaner tomorrow**. Take the first step – **start your Energy Community journey now!**

4.2. Video 2: Overcoming barriers in Energy Communities

After introducing the concept of an Energy Community in Video 1, the aim of the second video of the series is to inspire individuals interested in establishing or supporting Energy Communities. The video showcases examples and best practices from existing European initiatives and Energy Communities to overcome a range of barriers encountered when initiating an Energy Community journey. It emphasizes the availability of knowledge, tools, and resources from various European initiatives, catering

to those familiar with Energy Communities but also to newcomers exploring the concept for the first time. The content of this video covers best practices and tips for addressing a wide range of barriers, including technical, financial, operational, participation, user engagement, legal, and regulatory barriers.

Complementary written materials expand on the video's themes, including direct links to specific resources and references for further exploration from European initiatives. The written materials also offer detailed insights into available online tools and resources related to each barrier. The English script for Video 2 is provided below.

Box 2. Script of Video 2 on Overcoming barriers in Energy Communities available in the Training Hub of the LIFE-BECKON One-Stop-Shop Platform.

Introduction

Welcome to the **vibrant world of Energy Communities**, a dynamic force driving the **smart energy transition**. This video is your ticket to discover case studies and best practices that will empower you to face potential barriers and create successful Energy Community projects.

Insiders and Outsiders

In the realm of Energy Communities, there are **insiders** and **outsiders** – those that are already well informed and those eager to join the energy revolution. **Insiders** are the **experts**, the **pioneers** who have already embarked on this journey. Think of **energy cooperatives**, **proactive municipalities**, or **forward-thinking SMEs**. And then there are the **outsiders** – the **dreamers**, the **newcomers**, the ones ready to be **part of the change**. These can be **everyday citizens**, **ambitious municipalities**, **dedicated associations**, or **innovative investors**.

Inspiration from other European Initiatives

Whether you identify as an outsider or an insider, we have **got you covered**. Our mission is to **share essential knowledge**, **inspire** with real-life cases, and try to eventually **turn outsiders into insiders**. And in this, **we are not alone!** There is a wide range of other **remarkable European initiatives** that can further **spark your Energy Community journey, no matter where you stand**. Lightness, Decide4energy, Up-stairs, COME RES, and so many more have been contributing to the energy transition, offering knowledge, tools, and resources, to both insiders and outsiders.

Overcoming barriers

Every adventure, though, has its **challenges**, and Energy Communities are no exception. There are **various barriers** you may have to deal with throughout your journey. To overcome **technical barriers**, a good tip is to use available digital tools to perform pre-feasibility analysis and techno-economic prediction to have a strong and solid foundation for your initiative. Remember also to engage Distribution System Operators to promote cost-effectiveness and attract better business opportunities. Data collection challenges can also be daunting; so, make sure to prioritize privacy, build trust, and use digital tools.

For facing **financial and operational barriers**, the recommendation is to engage diverse relevant actors using available tools and take advantage of our Opportunity Hub in our One-Stop-Shop Platform to connect with the right people in your area. Address governance challenges, find profitable solutions, and develop transparent business models with tariffs for renewable energy. Remember also to always involve users to ensure they understand the benefits and conditions for participating in the market.

To overcome **participation and user engagement barriers**, consider to horizontally co-create solutions through effective and continuous communication with all actors, as well as leverage climate awareness, municipal support, and profit opportunities. Another tip is to emphasize in long-term engagement building trust with your connections, to be inclusive, and to prioritize accessible language while making sure everyone understands the topic addressed.

Overcoming **regulatory and legal barriers** involves clarifying national regulations, studying EU-wide variations, and collaborating with Distribution System Operators for cost-effective solutions.

Community energy actors play a crucial role in supporting governments to create an enabling legal framework, using guidance and policy advocacy for promoting Energy Communities.

And lastly, don't forget that clear communication is key when tackling any of these barriers!

Closing

Utilize the knowledge to fuel your Energy Community projects and stay tuned in the LIFE-BECKON One-stop-shop Platform for more inspiration. Your journey has just begun, and the path ahead is bursting with possibilities!

4.3. Video 3: Stakeholder engagement in Energy Communities

Video 3 emphasizes the crucial role of engaging all relevant stakeholders in Energy Communities and collaboratively shaping their sustainable future. It defines stakeholders and provides specific examples of types of stakeholders relevant to Energy Communities. Stressing the importance of early engagement, the video suggests key questions for designing effective stakeholder engagement strategies. It also offers suggestions and tips on language use, expectation management, as well as on meaningful and effective communication with stakeholders that are useful to consider when designing the stakeholder engagement strategy.

The complementary written materials mirror the video's content, highlighting the importance of effective engagement of and communication with the stakeholders relevant to Energy Communities. These materials include valuable resources and references for further insights. The English script for Video 3 is available below.

Box 3. Script of Video 3 on Stakeholder Engagement in Energy Communities available in the Training Hub of the LIFE-BECKON One-Stop-Shop Platform.

Introduction

Welcome to the **vibrant world of Energy Communities**, a dynamic force driving the **smart energy transition**. In this video we will explore how to involve the right voices at the right time in your Energy Community journey, co-creating with them a thriving, sustainable future.

Stakeholders

Stakeholders, also known as Energy Community Actors, are the **heartbeat of every Energy Community**. They are not just entities, but people with **diverse backgrounds and roles**, weaving together different sectors in a meaningful collaboration towards a **common vision**. They come from the **Industry & the Business sector**, the **Academia**, the **Government & the Public sector**, and of course the **Civil Society**. Coming from the civil society, **citizens** are the **real power** behind your journey's progress. Involving citizens makes it possible to **meet real and local needs** and foster **social acceptance**. Having them on board can also **spark creativity and innovation** and increase their sense of **ownership** upon the Energy Community, also securing their **long-lasting support**.

Stakeholder Engagement

Stakeholder engagement is a **form of art**; the art of involving the **right people and entities at the right time**. When conceptualizing your engagement approach, different stakeholders might be

more relevant and necessary to engage with at different times. This is why you need to ask yourselves: **What** are we aiming to tackle in each phase? **Who** and **when** do we need on board? **What roles** can the stakeholders play? and **What** is the level of engagement we expect from each stakeholder? And remember...it's important from the very beginning to set up **clear expectations** for your stakeholders, clearly defining your **goal**, the **scope** of their involvement and any potential **limitations**.

To fruitfully engage with your stakeholders, it's also important to **talk their language**. Not every person or entity has the same background and knowledge and not everyone has the same understanding on Energy Communities and the work you are doing. Remember to use **simple terminology and examples** to get your ideas across. Ticking those boxes and thinking upon interesting ways to involve your stakeholders, will allow you to have a **meaningful engagement with an added value** both for them and your Energy Community.

Communication strategies

The key to effective stakeholder management relies on skilful communication strategies. These tailored approaches will keep your stakeholders, **tuned in, involved, and truly passionate** about the community's initiatives. When mapping out your strategy it's important to define **clear and realistic objectives, tailor your approaches** for each unique stakeholder group and craft an **engaging mix of activities** to serve various **preferences**. And don't forget to be **adaptable and flexible**, embrace inclusivity and transparency and **be open and receptive to feedback** from your stakeholders.

Closing

For diving deeper into stakeholder engagement, explore the rich resources waiting for you at the LIFE-BECKON One-Stop-Shop Platform. Your journey is only taking its first steps, and the road ahead with boundless opportunities is waiting for you!

4.4. Video 4: Governance models and legal structures of Energy Communities

Video 4 highlights the pivotal role of governance structures in ensuring the resilience of Energy Communities. It delves into the various benefits of cultivating a robust governance model, including resource efficiency, accountability, and objectives achievement. Highlighting the importance of a clear organisational structure, it suggests the establishment of a core working group for the Energy Community, as well as a set of guiding questions that can

help the group on defining the community's governance structure.

Moreover, the video underscores important considerations when selecting a governance model, encompassing project size, available funding resources, and relevant regulations at local and national levels. It also provides a range of detailed examples of legal structures relevant to Energy Communities, offering valuable insights for decision-making. The video concludes by presenting seven guiding principles relevant to the governance models of Energy Communities, including, among others, open and voluntary membership, collaboration among Energy Communities, as well as autonomy and independence.

Complementary written materials further elaborate on the video's themes, emphasizing the importance of governance in Energy Communities. They offer practical tips, examples, and principles for selecting a suitable governance model and structuring governance effectively. These materials serve as valuable resources, providing references for further exploration. The English script for Video 4, focusing on Governance Models of Energy Communities, is provided below.

Box 4. Script of Video 4 on Governance models and legal structures for Energy Communities available in the Training Hub of the LIFE-BECKON One-Stop-Shop Platform.

Introduction

Welcome to the **vibrant world of Energy Communities**, a dynamic force driving the **smart energy transition**. In this video we will unveil **diverse governance structures**, explore **key principles**, and try to **address challenges**. Come along on this exploration to understand how governance models influence the resilience of Energy Communities!

Why Governance Matters

At the heart of an Energy Community's prosperity lies its governance structure, as it can secure **resource efficiency, accountability, and the achievement of objectives**. With a **transparent and inclusive model, community trust** blossoms, promoting **ongoing engagement**. Moreover, governance encourages **responsible management** of both energy and financial resources, maximizing their **impact** while promoting **sustainability**. Striving to be **voluntary, open, value-driven, and collective**, these communities need governance models that **balance diverse interests, ensure transparent decision-making, and foster financial sustainability**.

To start building your Energy Community, it is important to put in place a **clear organizational structure**. It is good to establish a **core working group** that will be responsible for the community in the long run and for exploring and consolidating collective ideas along the journey. It is important then to ask yourselves: **Who** are we? **What's our** collective **goal**? **Which** technical, financial, social, and political **resources** do we possess? **What challenges** might we face? **Which activities** and projects do we want to create?

Choosing governance model

Choosing a governance model for an Energy Community depends on various factors. For example: **Project size** determines the need for structured or grassroots approaches, while **funding sources**, such as public grants, or private investments can significantly impact governance. Additionally, **local, and national regulations** often favour specific models or determines governance structures for compliance. Finding the **right balance** among these factors is key to shaping an **effective governance model tailored to the needs of any Energy Community**. There are various legal structures for Energy Communities you can consider when working on your community's governance model.

These include **Cooperatives**, a prevailing model benefitting members; **Community trusts and Foundations**, focusing on social value and local development; **Limited Partnerships**, distributing responsibilities and profits among actors, as well as **Public-Private Partnerships** that aim to ensure energy provision and community benefits, involving local authorities, citizens, and businesses; **Non-profit customer-owned enterprises, structures employed by communities to manage independent grid networks; and Public utility companies**, that are typically operated by municipalities and they invest in and manage essential utilities on behalf of taxpayers and citizen.

Governance Building Principles

When creating Energy Communities and thinking upon their governance structure, there are **seven foundational principles** that can guide you: Principle 1 advocates for **Open and Voluntary Membership**, for fostering **inclusivity and diversity**, aligning with **community goals**, and promoting

openness and voluntary participation. Principle 2, **Democratic Member Control** is about ensuring **equal decision-making power.** **Representation and accountability mechanisms** ensure **fair** governance.

Moving to Principle 3, **Member Economic Participation**, is related to the way members of an Energy Community **contribute, gain rights, and enjoy incentives,** fostering active involvement and **benefit sharing.** Principle 4, **Autonomy and Independence**, underscores the importance of **collective ownership** and **decision-making** to safeguard the community's **economic and financial autonomy.** Principle 5, **Education, Training, and Information**, emphasises on the community's commitment to educating members on energy matters, promoting an energy-efficient lifestyle.

Principle 6, **Cooperation between Energy Communities**, stresses the importance of **collaboration for success**, where **experienced communities support newer ones,** fostering **mutual growth.** Finally, Principle 7, **Concern for Community**, showcases Energy Communities' unique approach **prioritising environmental, economic, and social benefits over financial profits.** This principle justifies **special policy support** and emphasises the **broader well-being of an Energy Community.**

Closing

As you move forward, remember...**governance is key to robust projects.** Consider your Energy Community's unique aspects, collaborate, and let these principles lead you. Your role in shaping resilient Energy Communities is pivotal—unleash the boundless possibilities!

4.5. Video 5: Regulation highlights for Energy Communities

Video 5 aims to shed light on regulations and the role they can have in steering a sustainable energy future. It explores the intricate landscape of European Union (EU) policies, specifically spotlighting the Recast Renewable Energy Directive⁷ and the Internal Electricity Market Directive⁸, originating from the Clean Energy for All Europeans Package⁹. These directives serve as pivotal blueprints, empowering Energy Communities to transition

from passive consumers to dynamic participants actively shaping the sustainable energy future.

The collaborative implementation of EU directives emerges as a central theme, emphasizing the convergence of regulators, governments, local authorities, and community members. The video also delves into the critical transposition of EU legislation into national laws, highlighting the necessity of integration and alignment with Energy Community definitions. Effortless awareness is stressed through tools like the REScoop Transposition Tracker¹⁰, enabling stakeholders to navigate the evolving regulatory landscape. Additionally, the video underscores the dynamic nature of Energy Community regulations and the importance of context specificity, highlighting the need to stay connected with national legislators and energy agencies for real-time updates.

⁷ [Recast Renewable Energy Directive](#)

⁸ [Internal Electricity Market Directive](#)

⁹ [Clean Energy for All Europeans Package](#)

¹⁰ [REScoop Transposition Tracker](#)

Ultimately, the video advocates for active participation in the Energy Community movement, portraying regulations not merely as legal constraints but as catalysts for a sustainable energy future. The English script for Video 5 is provided below.

Box 5. Script of Video 5 on Regulation highlights for Energy Communities available in the Training Hub of the LIFE-BECKON One-Stop-Shop Platform.

Introduction

Welcome to the **vibrant world of Energy Communities**, a dynamic force driving the **smart energy transition**. Join us as we uncover the crucial role of regulations in **steering the transformative journey of Energy Communities!**

EU's Regulatory Framework on Energy Communities

The **policies and regulations** of the European Union can be **tricky** to grasp as they are **constantly changing**. Not understanding them might mean **missing out on opportunities**. Therefore, exploring the policy and regulatory landscape can help **decode policies and support**. Born from the Clean Energy for All Europeans Package, Energy Communities signify a **shift from passive consumers to active participants**, rewriting the rules of engagement. At a European Union level, there are two **key Legislative acts** that define Energy Communities: the **Recast Renewable Energy Directive** and the **Internal Electricity Market Directive**. These two directives are **not just legal jargon**. They are the **blueprints for unleashing the potential of Energy Communities across the European Union**, and those that breathe life into both types of Energy Communities.

EU Directives Implementation

The regulatory process of Implementing EU directives has 3 main stages: the **Policy Formulation at the European Union Level**, the detailed **Transposition into national legislation**, and finally the **Application and Enforcement** of the legislation. The participants in this process include **Regulators**, who shape the framework, **Governments**, that offer **crucial support** to the Energy Communities through funding, **Local authorities**, that also support the Communities through Capacity building and other support mechanisms, and lastly **Community Members** who are the **architects of change; those that participate in the development and operation of the Communities**.

Transposition of EU legislation into national level

Delving deeper into the **Transposition stage** and monitoring the way the **Directives are transposed into national legislation** is **vital**. For this process, the **integration of the definition of Energy Communities** needs to be considered. The **degree of integration** achieved in each Member State can be **monitored** by various means, including the **alignment with Energy Community definitions** as outlined in **national contexts** or the depth of elaboration on **principles stipulated in EU criteria**. Considering of **support schemes and frameworks** when incorporating EU directives into national laws is also **imperative**. **Member states** are the ones who assess and remove **unjustified regulatory barriers**, define **clear duties for the Distribution System Operators**, and ensure **transparent registration and licensing** procedures. **Fair tariff incentives, accessibility for vulnerable households, and financial tools**, are, among others, also essential elements the Member states would have to take into consideration.

Up-to-date Information on EC Regulation

Staying updated on EU regulations is important and **now very easy!** Thanks to the European Federation of Citizen Energy Cooperatives, and using the **REScoop Transposition Tracker**, you can now seamlessly **track the transposition of Energy Community definitions** across European Member States. There are also plenty of other **online resources and repositories** that are available for getting more information. As changes might often occur in regulation, contacting national legislators and energy agencies for the status of the regulation is always advised.

Closing

The complex world of regulations for Energy Communities is **not just about laws**; it's an epic **journey of empowerment**, where Communities **shape their energy destiny**. **Join the Energy Community movement**—where regulations **pave the way for a sustainable energy future!**

4.6. Video 6: Financing of Energy Communities and Public Aids

Video 6 covers two fundamental topics for Energy Communities as it explores the available financing options, the essential role public aids play, and the unparalleled support provided by Technical Assistance Offices (TAO) in shaping the narrative of community-driven Energy Initiatives. The exploration uncovers a multidimensional funding landscape, highlighting the vital contributions of Ministries, Authorities, Municipalities, and forward-

thinking TAO. These entities collaborate to establish regulatory frameworks, coordinate regional and national efforts, and provide essential support, acting as catalysts for the growth of Energy Communities.

Delving into the substantial financing challenges faced by Energy Communities, the video navigates through various funding forms, including self-financing, bank financing, crowdfunding, and alternative models, such as ethical or social loans. Additionally, it explains the complexities of financial avenues available to Energy Communities, offering insights into diverse strategies.

The video also covers the crucial role of EU Public Funds, such as financial subsidies and grants, in overcoming financial barriers and propelling the growth of Energy Communities. It introduces monitoring tools like REScoop Financial Tracker¹¹, facilitating effective fund utilization and empowering communities to unlock their full potential in the renewable energy realm. The English script for Video 6 is provided below.

Box 6. Script of Video 6 on Financing of Energy Communities and Public Aids available in the Training Hub of the LIFE-BECKON One-Stop-Shop Platform.

Introduction

Welcome to the **vibrant world of Energy Communities**, a dynamic force driving the **smart energy transition**. In this exploration, we will unveil the **pivotal role of public aids** and the **dynamic support offered by the Technical Assistance Offices**, shaping the narrative of community-driven Energy Initiatives.

Funding from different authority levels

Public aids serve as **catalysts for progress**, **propelling the growth** of Energy Communities and **fostering community participation**. They **operate on multiple levels**, orchestrated by **Ministries and Authorities, Municipalities**, and the **innovative Technical Assistance Offices**, paving the way for robust community-driven Energy Initiatives. **Ministries and Authorities** take centre stage by **establishing favourable regulatory frameworks, coordinating regional and national efforts**, and

¹¹ [REScoop Financial Tracker](#)

thoroughly **monitoring and evaluating progress**. They are the ones laying the foundation for effective public aid mechanisms.

Municipalities also step into the spotlight, playing **varied roles** in **building technical assistance, fostering community partnerships, and providing crucial support** for **local energy planning and policy development**. These offices act as **drivers of transformation**, cultivating an ecosystem that **supports the thriving of Energy Communities**. Next to that, they **leverage existing networks of Energy offices**, providing invaluable support to potential Energy Communities across municipalities, also ensuring a **seamless transition towards community-driven Energy Initiatives**.

Financing

Financing is a **significant challenge for Energy Communities**. They can be public or private, and come in various forms. These forms may include **self-financing, bank financing, subsidies and grants, crowdfunding, crowdlending, financial lease**, as well as other **alternative financing models** like **ethical, green, or social loans**.

EU Public Funds

Public aids, such as financial subsidies and grants, are **key stimulants for the growth of Energy Communities** and play a **crucial role in overcoming financial barriers**. Exploring EU public funds, through monitoring tools, like the one offered by REScoop, ensures **effective utilization of financial resources** for the benefit of Energy Communities. Remember, it is **not only about securing funds**; it's about **unlocking the full potential of your community in the renewable energy realm**. From **understanding financial subsidies to exploring innovative financing options, or leveraging the support of local authorities, you** hold the keys to energizing your community. The Technical Assistance Office stands as your ally, ready to **guide and support you** in that.

Closing

As you embark on this transformative journey, remember, **it's not just about energy**; it's a **narrative of community resilience, empowerment, and sustainable progress**. Your community's energy story awaits its dynamic protagonist. Gear up and be the driving force in your community's green evolution!

4.7. Video 7: Technical and technological considerations for Energy Communities

Video 7 on technical and technological considerations for Energy Communities constitutes a comprehensive exploration of the challenges and solutions these communities encounter as they transition towards sustainability. As these communities shift towards renewable energy and efficient consumption, they grapple with intricate challenges. Coordination across the energy value chain introduces complexities in managing, supplying, and storing surplus energy, demanding thorough control system oversight.

Recognizing the uniqueness of each Energy Community, the video emphasizes the absence of a universal solution to their inherent technical issues. In the context of smart energy transition, complexities heighten with the shift from concentrated to distributed energy production and a focus on renewables. In addition,

video 7 navigates through diverse technologies, from small-scale wind turbines to photovoltaic systems, highlighting the need for tailored attention in each case at hand.

Understanding operational principles is crucial; thus, practical resources like a solar power installation checklist and tips from the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform are also provided. The video closes urging viewers to embrace complexities, learn from difficulties, and celebrate milestones in the dynamic evolution of their energy journey. The English script for Video 7 is provided below.

Box 7. Script of Video 7 on Technical and technological considerations for Energy Communities available in the Training Hub of the LIFE-BECKON One-Stop-Shop Platform.

Introduction

Welcome to the **vibrant world of Energy Communities**, a dynamic force driving the **smart energy transition**. In this video, we navigate the landscape of technical and technological challenges and solutions that these communities face as they strive for sustainability.

Technical and Technological complexities

As Energy Communities transition embracing **renewable energy, efficient consumption, and lower energy bills**, they can encounter a **variety of technical and technological complexities**. Moving from **passive consumption** involves **complex coordination across the different parts of the energy value chain**. Covering these parts, Energy Communities might encounter **different challenges**. For example, **managing, supplying, or storing surplus energy** requires careful coordination, thoroughly monitored by a control system.

Next to that, technical systems, both **hardware and software of an Energy Community**, demand **continuous attention and service**. **The more complex the system, the greater the need for maintenance**. However, it is important to acknowledge that **every Energy Community faces its unique set of challenges**. **There is no one-size-fits-all solution**, and technical issues are inherent in the operation of Energy Communities. Understanding the operational principles becomes essential for maintaining a **reliable, long-term operation**.

Technical and Technological considerations and smart energy transition

As we witness the **evolution towards smart energy transition**, the **complexities increase**. The shift from **concentrated to distributed energy production**, the **decrease in fossil fuel utilization**, and the **emphasis on renewable resources** all contribute to this changing landscape. In the realm of Energy Communities, the complexities vary with the intricacy of their energy systems; **simplicity often signifies reliability**. However, **as systems grow more intricate, demand for technical service escalates**.

Small-scale wind turbines, for example, require regular technical attention, compared to Photovoltaic systems that require minor technical service. Common technical considerations encompass **software updates, and control system optimization** — tasks often **managed by active members of the Energy Community**. While active members contribute significantly, some complexities mandate **professional expertise for seamless operation**, as for example with blown fuses or with device-specific problems. Understanding these technical aspects is crucial in **optimizing energy system performance**. Yet, it's crucial to recognize that there is **no universal solution for these challenges**.

To assist in this journey, we offer a **checklist for solar power installations**, outlining **necessary steps from obtaining permits to system activation**. Operations and maintenance are highlighted as crucial elements for the continued reliability of solar power systems, and in our LIFE-BECKON One-Stop-Shop Platform you can find some tips and tricks to further assist you. Delving into **other technical options** in Energy Communities, including **solar power, storage, heat pumps, electric vehicles, and batteries**, we recognize the **distinctiveness of each Energy Community**. Technical

considerations span a wide spectrum, and **there is no universal solution for all**. You can find some inspiration for your unique Energy Community in our LIFE-BECKON One-Stop-Shop Platform.

Closing

Energy Communities **thrive on an ongoing narrative**, an ever-evolving journey. It's a **tale of challenges, solutions, and perpetual adaptation** to a changing energy landscape. Remember, you are part of a dynamic adventure. **Embrace complexities, learn from hurdles, and celebrate each milestone**. Every step forward in your community's energy evolution is a **reason for celebration**.

4.8. Video 8: Operation of Energy Communities

Video 8 on the Operation of Energy Communities uncovers the complexities of the operational phase when setting up an Energy Community, harmonizing sustainability commitment with precise oversight and monitoring. Community members collaborate seamlessly, addressing legal, technical, and community-oriented aspects crucial for ongoing success. The video emphasizes monitoring tools, such as the Logical Framework Matrix from the LIFE-

BECKON project¹², actively steering communities toward sustainable practices.

In the operational phase, the video explores maintenance within Energy Communities, encompassing diverse aspects such as community dynamics, staff dedication, financial sustainability, support networks, technical infrastructure, and community engagement. This holistic approach to maintenance is portrayed as the cornerstone for achieving collective goals, fostering diversity, ensuring resilience, and advancing towards a sustainable future. Maintenance, in this context, goes beyond the traditional understanding of repairing physical structures; instead, it encompasses various aspects crucial for the sustained success of Energy Communities, including staff dedication, financial sustainability, support networks, technical infrastructure, and community engagement.

Additionally, the video encourages exploration of the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform and Energy Community Platform¹³ for valuable insights and resources. The English script for Video 8 is provided below.

Box 8. Script of Video 8 on Operation of Energy Communities available in the Training Hub of the LIFE-BECKON One-Stop-Shop Platform.

Introduction

Welcome to the **vibrant world of Energy Communities**, a dynamic force driving the **smart energy transition**. In this video, we centre our focus on the operational phase of Energy Communities, where the commitment to sustainability meets precise oversight, strategic scheduling, and vigilant monitoring.

Energy Communities in Operational phase

As an Energy Community reaches the operational phase, the focus **transitions to the day-to-day complexities that sustain its vitality**. Community members **work in harmony** to ensure **seamless operations**, constantly **evaluating and fine-tuning performance**. The operational phase is a **multifaceted stage** that demands attention to **legal, technical, and community-oriented aspects**. From **regular documentation** to **financial balance sheets**, **quality control checklists** to

¹² The Logical Framework Matrix will be available by March 2024 upon free registration in the Guidance Hub of the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform.

¹³ [Energy Community Platform](#)

maintenance guidelines—each element plays a **crucial role in the ongoing success of an Energy Community**.

Monitoring and evaluation

For Energy Communities, monitoring and evaluation is essential in **not just understanding the present state** but in **actively steering them towards more sustainable and efficient practices for the future**. One crucial tool for monitoring and evaluation within Energy Communities is the **Logical Framework Matrix**, also known as the **logical framework** or **Logframe approach**. Developed in the LIFE-BECKON project, the log-frame approach is a **structured management tool** that **condenses essential project elements into a table format**. This framework supports **planning, execution, and evaluation throughout the operational cycle**, giving you a synthetic and comprehensive overview to check where your Energy Community is standing at any given moment.

Maintenance

Let's now explore the **comprehensive realm of maintenance**, delving into **community dynamics, staff dedication, financial sustainability, support networks, technical infrastructure, and community engagement**. **Community maintenance** is key, managing Energy Communities, promoting **diversity among members**, and refining **collective visions and decision-making rules**. It builds a **strong foundation** for the community's **collective goals**. Moving on to **staff maintenance**, the focus is on **nurturing commitment and competence**. **Diversity and entrepreneurial skill sets** are essential components that contribute to the **resilience and adaptability** of the Energy Community.

Financial maintenance is vital for community viability, requiring **careful monitoring of operations, revenue streams, and investments**. A stable financial foundation fosters **trust**, ensuring **sustained growth**. **Support maintenance** strengthens community backing through **network expansion, political advocacy, and raising public awareness**. It fosters **broader understanding of Energy Communities** and community engagement.

Technical maintenance forms the **backbone for reliable operation**. It is not just about services; it is an **investment in monitoring**, ensuring the **seamless growth of energy production**, and keeping a precise record for future improvements. Finally, **network maintenance** is crucial, demanding **continual local and regional growth and recognition**. Sharing knowledge through intermediary organizations and driving transformative change in the energy sector are pivotal for the **community's collective vision**. During this operational phase, remember to explore our **LIFE-BECKON One-Stop-Shop Platform** and as well as **Energy Community Platform** for valuable **insights, good practices, and essential resources** on follow-up, scheduling, and monitoring

Closing

Here's to **embracing the operational challenges, celebrating the continuous growth** of your Energy Community, and **sustaining a collective vision** for a **greener and more resilient future**. Welcome to the **ongoing success of your community energy endeavors**.

5. Open Innovation Journey (OIJ) as a tool in the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform

To facilitate practical application, the OIJ methodology is transformed into a user-friendly tool that will be accessible on the Training Hub of the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform upon free registration. This adaptation aims to present a straightforward and usable format for individuals and organizations interested in Energy Communities. The methodology, comprising a collection of tools, will be displayed step by step through downloadable templates on the platform. Each template provides explicit instructions and timing suggestions for practical implementation. Following a modular approach, users can choose specific tools tailored to their co-creation needs for Energy Communities, with each tool functioning as a standalone option.

Each step of the methodology and the corresponding canvas with instructions will be available for downloading as a .pdf, thus allowing users to print it for use offline. A description of each of the main steps of the OIJ methodology with their corresponding canvas is presented below. For details on how to implement the methodology and detailed instructions on how to implement each step, refer to D2.1 “Open Innovation Journeys”, available at the LIFE-BECKON OSS Training Hub upon free registration.

Step 1. Purpose

Understanding the purpose is key to ensure a successful OIJ. This step focuses on clarifying the objectives of municipalities in creating an Energy Community or support its set up. In a 30-minute session, team members individually express their reasons for setting up an Energy Community, using sticky notes. These ideas are then organized and discussed as a group, aiming to arrive at a shared purpose. The key question throughout is: Why does the municipality want to establish or support an Energy Community, and what transformative goals does it aim to achieve? This sets the foundation for the subsequent steps in the OIJ.

Figure 6. OIJ Step 1: Purpose. ©ENoLL 2023. This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International License.

Step 2. SWOT Analysis

Analysis is a pivotal stage in the OIJ for Energy Community development. In a 30-minute interactive session, the team evaluates the Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats related to the Energy Community’s purpose. Through a brainstorming exercise, ideas are captured on white sticky notes and placed in the SWOT matrix. This process identifies key factors influencing the Energy Community’s future and supports the strategic approach for its development. Once the team agrees on the SWOT findings, they proceed to the next step in the OIJ.

Step 2. SWOT Analysis

Objective:
Identify key factors (positive and negative) influencing the future development of your Energy Community and Living Lab, and identify opportunities and threats.

Instructions:

- As a team, start brainstorming about your Strengths, Weaknesses, Opportunities, and Threats.
- Write each idea individually on a white sticky note
- Put it where it belongs in the matrix.

Strengths

Beneficial aspects or capabilities of the organization or place, which includes human competencies, capabilities, financial resources, products and services, citizens goodwill and brand loyalty.

Weaknesses

Characteristics that place a city or organization at a disadvantage relative to others. Holds the organization/city place from its ability to attain the core goal and influence its growth.

Opportunities

Chances to make greater profits in the environment - External attractive factors that represent the reason for a city or an organization to continue to develop and become more successful.

Threats

External elements in the environment that could cause trouble - External factors, beyond a city's control, which could place the city's mission or operation at risk. Threats are uncontrollable.

Proposed time: 30 minutes

Click to select me, then copy me!

	Helpful to achieving the objectives	Harmful to achieving the objective
Internal Origin (attributes of the organization)	<div style="font-size: 48px; font-weight: bold; color: #8BC34A;">S</div> <p style="font-size: 8px;">Examples - Abundant financial resources, available human resources, committed member, well-known brand name, committed employees.</p>	<div style="font-size: 48px; font-weight: bold; color: #FF9800;">W</div> <p style="font-size: 8px;">Examples - Limited financial resources, Weak spending on R&D, lack of commitment of citizens, Weak image, Limited management skills, Under-trained employees.</p>
External origin (attributes of the environment)	<div style="font-size: 48px; font-weight: bold; color: #00BCD4;">O</div> <p style="font-size: 8px;">Examples - Rapid economic growth of a country, new international trends, changing customer needs/tastes, new uses for product discovered, government deregulation, national subsidies</p>	<div style="font-size: 48px; font-weight: bold; color: #9C27B0;">T</div> <p style="font-size: 8px;">Examples - Entry of foreign competitors, changing customer needs/tastes, rival cities adopt new strategies, increased government regulation (increase taxes), economic downturn.</p>

Figure 7. OIJ Step 2: SWOT Analysis. ©ENoLL 2023. This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International License.

Step 3. COCD Box

Originating from the Centre for Development of Creative Thinking (COCD), the COCD Box evaluates ideas based on originality and ease of implementation. COCD Box in the OIJ, a 20-minute interactive session, leverages the COCD Box tool to refine and select ideas generated during brainstorming. Participants use yellow, blue, and red stickers to categorize ideas as "How," "Now," or "Wow." The majority determines the colour placement in the box. The session concludes by developing the three most intriguing "Wow" ideas into comprehensive solutions, promoting creativity and innovation.

Step 3. COCD Box: How Now Wow Matrix

Objective:
Start thinking about potential solutions for your challenges and organise them into those you can implement easily, breakthrough ideas, and ideas for the future.

Instructions:

1. Brainstorm about possible ideas (>20) to approach your challenges and write them down on post its.
2. Each group member receives yellow, blue and red stickers. Individually select the "best" ideas and determine whether they are yellow (How), blue (Now) or red (Wow) ideas.
3. Arrange the COCD Box based on the majority of the color sticker on the idea.
4. Select the three most interesting ideas and finally develop three "Wow" ideas into three complete ideas. If necessary, several ideas can be combined into a single idea.

Proposed time: 20 minutes

Click to select me, then copy me!

	NON-FEASIBLE	Ideas for the future Dreams and challenges Visionary ideas Food for the brain Red ideas for tomorrow HOW
	Easy to implement Small / low risk Higher acceptance rate Examples available Quick wins NOW	Innovative ideas Potential breakthroughs Exciting ideas Distinctive ideas Can be implemented fast WOW
	COMMON IDEAS	INNOVATIVENESS ORIGINAL IDEAS

WOW
IDEA 1

WOW
IDEA 2

WOW
IDEA 3

© 0 1 2 3

Figure 8. OIJ Step 3: COCD Box. ©ENoLL 2023. This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International License.

Step 4. Stakeholder Mapping

Stakeholder Mapping in the OIJ is a 30-minute interactive session, vital for identifying key stakeholders in the quadruple-helix model - academia, public, private, and society. Guided by questions about roles, actions, recruitment, and engagement, the team maps stakeholders on a matrix, highlighting essential entities and identifying any gaps. This strategic mapping aligns with the quadruple-helix methodology, ensuring comprehensive stakeholder engagement in the Energy Community development.

Step 4. Stakeholder Mapping

Objective:
Identify all stakeholders that are needed to fulfil the purpose.

Instructions:

1. Individually, start thinking about any stakeholder that should be involved at any given time in the project.
2. Write each stakeholder in a separate post in the color that corresponds to the quadruple helix.
3. Move it to the matrix where you think it belongs.
4. If the stakeholder is already in the board, put your post it on top of the existing one.
5. As a group, discuss the stakeholders on the board and identify if any are missing.
6. Select the most important stakeholders in each quadrant and add a red star next to each of them.

Proposed time: 30 minutes

What is a Stakeholder?
People and/or organisations that are involved, interested, and/or influenced by the strategy and activities of the Energy Community and the Living Lab

How are stakeholders divided in the Quadruple Helix Model (QHM)?

Government & Public Sector	Industry & Business
Academia & Universities	Civil Society

Click to select me, then copy me!

© 0 1 2 3

Figure 9. OIJ Step 4: Stakeholder Mapping. ©ENoLL 2023. This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International License.

Step 5. Power Vs Interest Matrix

A 30-minute interactive session available, where stakeholders identified in earlier steps, marked as most important in Step 4, are placed on a matrix categorizing them based on their power and interest in the project. As a group, stakeholders are discussed individually to assess their level of power and interest, determining their placement in the identified quadrant. This session is pivotal for tailoring engagement strategies, ensuring effective management of stakeholders with varying degrees of influence and interest in the project.

Figure 10. OIJ Step 5: Power vs Interest Matrix. ©ENoLL 2023. This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International License.

Step 6. OIJ & Validation

Inspired by both the LLIP¹⁴ and the phases to set up an Energy Community used within LIFE-BECKON. The OIJ & validation step, designed for on-site interactive sessions, involves presenting previous steps to a small representation of targeted stakeholders. The internal OIJ is suggested to be developed on-site by the municipality team within 90 minutes per solution, including a 2-hour workshop with stakeholders. During this workshop, the team presents the purpose of the Energy Community and identified solutions, summarizing all previous OIJ steps. The validation process includes copying main stakeholders into the designated box, filling in the OIJ vertically following the different stages, and repeating the process in an in-person workshop with representatives from each stakeholder group. Adaptations are made based on stakeholder feedback, ensuring a robust and validated OIJ for each stakeholder group.

¹⁴ Mastelic, J. (2019). Stakeholder’s engagement in the co-design of energy conservation interventions: The case of the Energy Living Lab.

Step 6. Open Innovation Journey (OIJ)

Objective:
Define the main user / customer open innovation journey (OIJ)

Instructions:

1. Start by copying your main stakeholders identified in step 2 in the designated box.
2. With your team, by following the Living Lab Integrative Process stages and steps, and phases to set up an energy community, start filling in the OIJ vertically (start from the column **Select a Practice**).
3. Use the notes next to the first column to guide you into filling in the OIJ.
4. Repeat the process in an in-person workshop with representatives from your main stakeholders.
5. Repeat the OIJ for each stakeholder group from the quadruple helix.
6. If needed, adapt the internal OIJ according to the comments from the stakeholders.

INTERNAL OIJ

STAKEHOLDER GROUP: Civil Society

SOLUTION

Proposed time: 60 minutes + 30 minutes for final adjustments

My main stakeholders from the stakeholder group	Living Lab Integrative Process		
	PROBLEM SPACE	SOLUTION SPACE	DEPLOYMENT SPACE
Phases to set up an Energy Community	Initiation	Design	Implementation & Operation
Stakeholder Goals			
Stakeholder Activities			
Stakeholder Touch Points			
Stakeholder experience			
Value for the Stakeholder			
Expected outcomes			
Results achieved			

VALIDATION OIJ

Proposed time: 120 minutes

My main stakeholders from the stakeholder group	Living Lab Integrative Process		
	PROBLEM SPACE	SOLUTION SPACE	DEPLOYMENT SPACE
Phases to set up an Energy Community	Initiation	Design	Implementation & Operation
Stakeholder Goals			
Stakeholder Activities			
Stakeholder Touch Points			
Stakeholder experience			
Value for the Stakeholder			
Expected outcomes			
Results achieved			

Figure 11. OIJ Step 6: Open Innovation Journey Template and Validation. ©ENoLL 2023. This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International License.

Step 7. Implementation Plan

In the final step of the OIJ, the process embraces the dynamic and iterative nature of implementing Energy Communities. Learning from historical planning approaches, the implementation plan is seen as a fluid, adaptive strategy, emphasizing that the implementation process itself is the key focus of evaluation. Recognizing the evolving landscape, the Energy Community implementation is viewed as dynamic, requiring regular reviews every six months. The 100-minute interactive session engages the internal Energy Community team, guiding them to draft the initial version of the implementation plan for all main stakeholders involved. This approach ensures a flexible and responsive strategy aligned with the changing needs and objectives of Energy Communities.

Step 7. OIJ Implementation Plan

Objective:
Draft the first version of the implementation plan of your OIJ for all your main stakeholders.

Instructions:

1. Copy the main stakeholder selected in STEP 2 for all stakeholder groups, which are the same ones you used for creating the OIJs.
2. With the Living Lab team, by following the Living Lab Integrative Process stages and steps, and the phases to set up an Energy Community, start filling in the implementation plan horizontally for each of the main stakeholders you identified in STEP 2. Click on the corresponding cell to add information and ideally, add also an expected date in which you are planning on doing the activity.
 - a. You can combine cells by selecting the ones you want to combine and clicking on the button that appears on top (or below) the cells
3. Repeat for all stakeholders in each stakeholder group.

Proposed time: 100 minutes

Living Lab Integrative Process	Problem space		Solution space		Deployment space		
	Empathise	Define	Ideate	Prototype	Test	Implement	Scale-up
Select a practice	Integrate stakeholders	Uncover barriers	Co-design plan	Pilot an intervention	Evaluate performance	Demonstrate system	Exploit the solution
STAKEHOLDER GROUP: Government & Public Sector							
Stakeholder 1							
Stakeholder 2							
STAKEHOLDER GROUP: Industry & Business							
STAKEHOLDER GROUP: Academia & Universities							
STAKEHOLDER GROUP: Civil Society							

Figure 12. OIJ Step 7: OIJ Implementation Plan. ©ENoLL 2023. This work is licensed under the Creative Commons Attribution-NonCommercial 4.0 International License.

6. LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform Training Hub: Accessibility and user experience

The development and integration of the training materials into the Training Hub of the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform will be carefully executed with a dual focus on accessibility and a seamless user experience. This section elucidates the presentation of these materials on the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform, outlining key features and considerations that will contribute to an optimal user experience and enhanced accessibility for a diverse audience.

User-Centric Design philosophy

The integration of the developed training materials into the platform will stem from a user-centric design philosophy, influencing the entire architecture. Work Package 3 "Integrated services through One-Stop-Shop Platform" is dedicated to crafting an intuitive interface for the users. The platform acts as the gateway to the Training Hub, offering a rich repository of materials, including training videos, accompanied by complementary tools from the LIFE-BECKON Cookbook and written materials, the innovative OIJ, and the training materials from sister projects.

Cohesive integration for user-friendly experience

A cohesive integration strategy will be employed to provide users with a unified and streamlined experience. This user-friendly environment will facilitate accessibility and engagement, enabling users to seamlessly navigate through extensive content. This commitment to user-centricity ensures that the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform Training Hub will be a dynamic, interactive space that adapts to diverse preferences and needs.

Foundational commitment to accessibility

Accessibility is intertwined into the fabric of the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform, serving as a foundational guiding principle. Simple and generic language was deliberately chosen to resonate with a diverse audience. This linguistic strategy fosters inclusivity, inviting individuals from different backgrounds to engage meaningfully with the training materials.

Multilingual approach of the training videos

For the training videos, the accessibility aspect will be addressed through a comprehensive and multilingual approach. Each thematic video, stands as an individual entity on the platform, offering users a tailored and user-centric experience. The multilingual approach goes beyond inclusion, becoming an integral component that amplifies user choice and inclusivity.

Complementary written Materials and interaction

To enhance the user experience, each training video will be complemented by a downloadable slide deck. These written materials will then serve as a comprehensive resource, providing an in-depth exploration of each video's topic. Users will be able to actively engage in discussions and pose questions directly related to each video through the provided "Comments" section, fostering collaboration, and creating a vigorous learning space within the platform.

Strategic integration of OIJ

The OIJ, a cornerstone within the suite of training materials, will be strategically and seamlessly integrated into the LIFE-BECKON OSS Training Hub. This deliberate integration will demonstrate the Platform's commitment to offering users an immersive and cohesive learning experience. The OIJ methodology will unfold systematically, with each step presented as an independent entity, showcased through meticulously crafted downloadable templates.

A dynamic Training Hub

Beyond training materials, the dynamic LIFE-BECKON OSS Training Hub will evolve into a multifaceted space designed to foster continuous engagement and collaborative learning. A dedicated "Ideas" section will be available, inviting users to contribute suggestions for additional training materials, ensuring content remains relevant. Additionally, the proposed "Forum" section will function as an open space for discussion, amplifying the collaborative spirit, while the "Agenda and Events" section will serve as an information centre, keeping users informed about upcoming webinars and training sessions.

A transformative learning environment

The LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform Training Hub will transcend a traditional repository for training materials, emerging as a vibrant and interactive hub. Crafted to elevate the user experience, it will cultivate a collaborative learning environment. This Platform will underscore a steadfast commitment to accessibility, user-friendliness, and a rich array of interactive features. These elements will mirror the overarching goal of empowering a diverse spectrum of stakeholders in their collective journey toward comprehending, engaging with, and actively contributing to the intricate landscape of Energy Communities.

7. Training materials from Cookbook and sister projects

This section unfolds two key dimensions crucial to the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform's Training Hub. First, delve into the intricacies of the LIFE-BECKON Technical Assistance Cookbook. Developed under Work Package 1, this comprehensive guide caters to public authorities and promoters involved in Energy Community deployment. From self-assessment checklists to regulatory considerations, it is a practical resource for every stage of Energy Community development.

Beyond the Cookbook, we spotlight the collaborative efforts of European initiatives under the topic “Developing support mechanisms for Energy Communities and other citizen-led initiatives in the field of sustainable energy” (LIFE21-CET-ENERCOM) - often referred to as LIFE sister projects - aligned with the theme of sustainable energy initiatives. United under the LIFE21-CET-ENERCOM topic, these projects will contribute diverse resources to the platform.

7.1. LIFE-BECKON Technical Assistance Cookbook

The LIFE-BECKON Technical Assistance Cookbook, developed under Work Package 1 “Comprehensive Cookbook for technical assistance”, serves as a comprehensive guide for public authorities and promoters engaged in facilitating the deployment of Energy Communities. This Cookbook covers various aspects, including technical, financial, regulatory, tendering, and participatory dimensions. It begins with a self-assessment checklist, allowing promoters to assess the maturity of their initiatives. The Cookbook comprises sections on needs assessment analysis, technical support, financial and operational support, participatory processes, regulatory and legal considerations, and quality control. The participatory process and user engagement are emphasized, with guidelines and methodologies for inclusive community involvement. The Cookbook addresses regulatory and legal aspects, providing guidance on compliance, governance models, and tendering procedures. Additionally, it incorporates quality control, monitoring, and evaluation support.

The output is a user-friendly Cookbook structured in five-step phases: initiation, technical design, legal design, setup and implementation, and monitoring and reporting. It acts as a practical tool, guiding interested parties through the creation and implementation of successful Energy Communities, tailored to their specific needs and stages of development.

Its significance is further underscored as it serves as the backbone of the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform, seamlessly incorporated into the platform's architecture. This strategic integration ensures that the wealth of knowledge encapsulated in the Cookbook is effortlessly accessible within the platform, and more specifically, through the Guidance Hub, fostering a cohesive and streamlined approach to navigating the complexities of Energy Community development.

Furthermore, while a substantial portion of the LIFE-BECKON Technical Assistance Cookbook resides within the comprehensive Guidance Hub, a strategic linkage is also established with the Training Hub. Within the Training Hub, specific tools and resources extracted from the Cookbook are planned to be intricately linked, fostering a cohesive connection between these two pivotal sections of the platform. These tools and resources will be identified with project partners WeGlobal and R2M Solution Spain when the platform architecture is finalised¹⁵. The deliberate integration ensures that the practical tools and

¹⁵ Expected in March 2024.

guidelines provided by the Cookbook are readily accessible to stakeholders engaging in training initiatives. By creating this seamless bridge between the Guidance and the Training Hub, LIFE-BECKON enhances the Platform's user experience, offering a unified and integrated approach to skill development and knowledge acquisition within the realm of Energy Community deployment.

7.2. LIFE Sister projects

The topic “Developing support mechanisms for Energy Communities and other citizen-led initiatives in the field of sustainable energy” (LIFE21-CET-ENERCOM) is part of the “Programme for Environment and Climate Action” (LIFE)¹⁶. This topic, through which LIFE-BECKON has received co-funding from the European Commission, plays a pivotal role in advancing sustainable Energy Communities and citizen-led initiatives within the sustainable energy domain. Specifically crafted to empower citizens to play an active role in both their energy production and consumption, this program is strategically aligned with the European Union's overarching objectives of reducing greenhouse gas emissions and promoting the adoption of renewable energy sources.

Within the thematic scope of the LIFE21-CET-ENERCOM topic, an overarching and multifaceted approach is expected to underpin projects. The program adopts a comprehensive strategy with a focus on key areas, including the development and dissemination of best practices, essential training and capacity building initiatives, support for pilot projects, and active advocacy for policies conducive to the flourishing of Energy Communities.

A core principle of LIFE21-CET-ENERCOM is the expectation that funded projects, including LIFE-BECKON, embrace this holistic approach, ensuring a well-rounded contribution to the advancement of citizen-led sustainable energy endeavours. This comprehensive strategy aligns with the broader objectives of the European Union, emphasizing the active empowerment of citizens, reduction of greenhouse gas emissions, and promotion of renewable energy sources. The envisioned outcome is a more sustainable and equitable energy landscape, in line with the strategic goals set by the European Commission.

In addition to LIFE-BECKON, numerous projects funded under the LIFE21-CET-ENERCOM initiative, often referred to as LIFE sister projects, are actively contributing to the creation of Capacity Building materials. Recognizing the value of cross-fertilization, LIFE-BECKON is committed to sharing materials developed by them in the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform. This collaborative approach aims to enrich the knowledge-sharing environment and provide stakeholders with a diverse range of resources for effective Capacity Building.

Upon completion of the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform design and its subsequent launch¹⁷, we envision organizing bilateral calls with the Capacity Building leads from each sister project. These collaborative discussions will facilitate strategic decisions on the integration of capacity building materials from each project onto the Platform. The aim is to curate a cohesive and comprehensive collection of capacity building resources, ensuring relevance and coherence in supporting the broader objective of fostering sustainable Energy Communities. This process will enable a tailored approach, allowing each project's unique insights and expertise to contribute effectively to the collective knowledge-sharing environment provided by the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform.

LIFE-LOOP has taken the initiative to facilitate cross-fertilization efforts among sister projects. LIFE-LOOP actively supports the exchange of insights and materials among projects, fostering a collaborative

¹⁶ Link to topic details: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/opportunities/topic-details/life-2021-cet-enercom>

¹⁷ Expected in March 2024.

environment. Currently, 5 out of the 6 funded projects under the LIFE21-CET-ENERCOM topic are part of the cross-fertilization efforts led by LIFE-LOOP. Besides LIFE-BECKON, the projects are:

LIFE-LOOP: Collaboration between cities/regions and energy cooperatives as vehicles to accelerate the energy transition

LIFE-LOOP¹⁸ addresses governance challenges in Energy Communities, drawing on lessons from past projects like COMANAGE. It aims to overcome legal, administrative, financial, social, and organizational hurdles by creating an Energy

Communities Governance Framework. The project provides public authorities in Energy Community projects with a toolkit for streamlined management. Goals include supporting existing projects, fostering new community-owned energy initiatives, and establishing a transnational network and three Integrated Services Hubs in Spain, Poland, and Italy. LIFE-LOOP aims to ensure success and stimulate new initiatives across the EU.

TANDEMS: Energy Communities – Local Ownership of Power

TANDEMS¹⁹, a collaboration among Energy Cities, Electra, ZEZ, Cooperativa de Energie, and REScoop.eu, launches a program to empower local authorities and regions in achieving sustainable energy plans. The initiative accelerates community energy partnerships and projects in pilot areas such as Crete (Greece), Zagreb (Croatia), and Bistrita (Romania). With replication in satellite authorities, it aims to build capacity, unlock funding, simplify regulations, and incentivize participation in clean community energy initiatives, focusing on solar generation, energy efficiency, and exploring opportunities in various renewable sources.

COMANAGE: Developing a transnational governance and holistic integrated services framework supporting the sustainability of European Energy Communities

COMANAGE²⁰ addresses barriers to successful Energy Community projects, proposing a Governance Framework and Toolkit. It focuses on legal,

administrative, financial, social, and organizational hurdles, aiming to empower public authorities for effective project management. The project supports existing projects and encourages new community-owned initiatives. LIFE-COMANAGE plans to establish a network and Integrated Services Hubs in Spain, Poland, and Italy, advancing Energy Community projects across the EU.

ConnectHeat: Community Engagement for Clean Heat

ConnectHeat

ConnectHeat²¹ aims to create a policy framework for community energy initiatives in seven European target areas, focusing on decarbonizing heating and cooling. Overcoming sector barriers, the project includes diverse applications and technical solutions, collaborating with stakeholders, implementing pilot cases, and developing policy roadmaps. The

consortium anticipates substantial renewable energy generation, investments, policy development, and extensive training efforts.

¹⁸ [LIFE-LOOP project description](#)

¹⁹ [LIFE-TANDEMS project description](#)

²⁰ [LIFE-COMANAGE project description](#)

²¹ [ConnectHeat project description](#)

8. Conclusions and next steps

This document, D2.2 “Online Training Materials”, underscores the pivotal role of LIFE-BECKON's training materials in facilitating the growth and sustainability of Energy Communities. Guided by a collaborative spirit, the development process created eight thematic videos, multilingual written content, and the translation of the OIJ methodology into a tool—all seamlessly accessible through the Training Hub of the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform upon free registration. Additionally, these training materials will be shared with replicators engaged in Work Package 5 “Mass-replication, exploitation, dissemination and communication”, fostering mass replication and dissemination through the Open Call for replicators.

In tandem with stakeholder needs identified in D2.1 “Open Innovation Journeys” and the thematic areas outlined in the proposal stage, the training materials emerge as strategic catalysts, providing a structured and comprehensive approach to empower stakeholders in the journey of establishing, supporting, and sustaining Energy Communities. However, it's noteworthy to acknowledge that the absence of the LIFE-BECKON Cookbook during the initial stages of the training videos' production posed some critical challenges. The Cookbook, serving as a fundamental resource, was integral for comprehensive coverage and thematic alignment, and its delayed availability influenced the iterative refinement process.

The methodological approach employed for developing the training videos was thoughtfully designed to ensure a comprehensive foundation for knowledge dissemination. Notably, the training materials are meticulously tailored for accessibility and inclusivity. Embracing a user-friendly, multilingual, and modular format, these resources go beyond conventional training repositories. The development process, marked by iterative feedback loops with project partners, promoted not only quality, accuracy, and consistency but also a coverage of critical aspects spanning from defining Energy Community types to addressing barriers, governance models, stakeholder engagement strategies, regulations, financing options, and technical considerations.

The OIJ methodology, born out of ENOLL's expertise, serves as a strategic compass encapsulated in seven steps. Its modular format will take the shape of user-friendly templates on the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform, providing municipalities and other relevant stakeholders practical tools for co-creation tailored to their unique needs. The Training Hub, a cornerstone of the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform, is thoroughly designed with a user-centric approach, emphasizing accessibility and interactivity. It is the central repository hosting these training materials, ensuring a seamless learning experience for a diverse audience.

The dynamic Training Hub is not a static endpoint but a continuum. Strategic dialogues with sister projects, as envisioned by LIFE-LOOP, will deepen integration, guaranteeing a harmonized and enriched knowledge-sharing space. After the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform is launched - expected in March 2024 - and the training materials described in this deliverable are uploaded, the next steps involve the continuous enrichment of the Training Hub with additional materials from sister projects, creating a collaborative environment that nurtures sustainable energy initiatives. Simultaneously, feedback, improvements, and ideas for additions will be actively taken into consideration from the users of the LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform, to further enrich and improve the provided training materials. This two-way interaction will not only refine existing content but also guide the creation of new materials, ensuring the platform remains a dynamic and relevant space for continuous learning.

In summary, LIFE-BECKON training materials stand as a dynamic catalyst, thoroughly designed upon a collaborative vision. They not only empower stakeholders but also foster the growth of sustainable energy initiatives, propelling shared goals forward. Pioneering an ongoing journey of improvement and relevance in the vibrant landscape of Energy Communities, these resources embody adaptability. Striving for excellence, it becomes crucial to stay attuned to evolving stakeholder needs and industry trends. Regular assessments and updates are not just recommended; they are the keystones to keep the content fresh, ensuring alignment with emerging challenges and seizing opportunities on the horizon.

Annex – Slide decks as support written material for videos

The annex provides slide decks that complement the training videos available on the Training Hub of the LIFE-BECKON One-Stop-Shop Platform upon free registration, serving as supportive written materials. These slide decks are meticulously crafted to offer users a comprehensive resource, delving deeper into the topics covered in the videos. Each slide deck is designed to enhance understanding and retention, providing visual aids and additional explanations to reinforce key concepts presented in the videos. The inclusion of these slide decks aims to enrich the learning experience, catering to diverse learning styles and preferences. Users can download and reference these slide decks alongside the videos to gain a more thorough understanding of the subject matter and facilitate further exploration. To enhance accessibility and ensure inclusivity, the complementary written materials have been translated into eight European languages, aligning with the guidelines set forth by the Grant Agreement. These languages include Bulgarian, Danish, English, French, German, Finnish, Italian, and Spanish.

Video 1: Definition and benefits of Energy Communities

Definition and Benefits of Energy Communities

25 January 2024

LIFE-BECKON

Co-funded by the European Union

Introduction

LIFE-BECKON 2

Energy Communities are becoming more and more popular, since they provide one solution for the progress of smart energy transition.

In this Capacity Building Module, we **define Energy Communities**, unfolding the **different types**, the **similarities and differences** they share, as well as the **multiple benefits** they have to offer in the energy transition.

LIFE-BECKON 3

For who?

Videos are targeted to any stakeholder interested in energy communities:

- **Municipalities** supporting the creation of energy communities
- **Ministries** and **Public authorities** at local, regional and national levels
- **Energy agencies** and **Energy companies**
- **Local associations**
- **Investors** and **Renewable energy developers**
- **Consultants**
- **Citizens**

4

Energy Initiatives: Self-consumption and Energy Communities

5

New energy initiatives for individuals and communities

With the [Clean Energy for all Europeans package](#) European Commission introduced new provisions on the energy market design and frameworks for new energy initiatives. These include:

- **Collective self-consumption**
 - Constitutes a specific activity, not explicitly focusing on the organisational format.
- **Energy Communities**
 - Focus on organisational and market aspects.

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Collective self-consumption

Collective self-consumption can be defined as **jointly acting renewables self-consumers**.

- A group of at least two cooperating “renewables self-consumers who are located in the same building or multi-apartment block”.

Currently some countries already **allow collective self-consumption** on:

- **Building scale - e.g.**, inhabitants of one multi-apartment building share produced renewable electricity. Also connected installations such as a storage system can be shared.
- **Block scale - e.g.**, area is enlarged to more than one building (including neighbouring buildings via direct lines) and correspondingly more actors are involved.

i [Working paper Collective self-consumption and energy communities: Overview of emerging regulatory approaches in Europe of Compile project.](#)

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Definition of Energy Communities

8

Definition and types of Energy Communities

An Energy Community is an organization of individuals, families, or local entities that collaborate to produce, consume, and manage energy in a sustainable way

European commission has two definitions of an energy community:

- **Renewable Energy Community (REC)**
- **Citizen Energy Community (CEC)**

i [Clean Energy for all Europeans package](#) [Rural Energy Community Advisory Hub](#)

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Differences between Citizen (CEC) and Renewable (REC) Energy Communities

	Citizen Energy Communities (CEC)	Renewable Energy Communities (REC)
Geographical scope	Not bound to a specific vicinity	Must operate in the vicinity of owned/developed renewable energy projects
Activities	Operate in the electricity sector, technology-neutral	Focus primarily on renewable energy-related activities
Participants	Any actor can participate	Restricted to natural persons, local authorities, and MSMEs*
Autonomy	Decision-making not limited based on economic activity	Autonomy maintained excluding large-scale commercial energy actors*
Effective control	No restrictions on control	Control by MSMEs in proximity to the renewable energy project**

* excluding large-scale commercial energy actors
 ** excluding medium and large enterprises 10

Understanding the types of Energy Communities

While both types of Energy Communities share similarities, they are not entirely identical.

The primary vision of Energy Communities is to self-organize around energy-related initiatives, aiming to deliver services or other socio-economic advantages to their members and/or the surrounding community.

Common characteristics of the two types of Energy Communities are:

- In both CEC and REC participation is **open and voluntary** to all legal entities.
- The **primary objective** of both types is to deliver **environmental, economic, or social community benefits** to their members, shareholders, or the local regions in which they operate, rather than to generate financial profits, rather than to generate financial profits.
- Effective control is vested in citizens, local authorities, and small businesses that aren't already engaged in the energy sector.

[LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform – Guidance Hub](#)

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Possible activities of Citizen (CEC) and Renewable (REC) Energy Communities

Citizen Energy Communities (CEC)	Renewable Energy Communities (REC)
Electricity generation	RES generation
Energy efficiency services	Energy efficiency services (connected to RES supply)
E-mobility	E-mobility from RES
Supply	RES supply
Aggregation	RES aggregation
Community network/local energy system	RES sharing
Public grid	RES self-consumption
Other energy services	District heating and cooling (RES)
Sharing	
Self-consumption	

[LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform – Guidance Hub](#)

* RES: Renewable Energy Resources 12

Phases of setting up Energy Communities

Benefits of Energy Communities

Benefits of Energy Communities

Energy communities offer a wide range of benefits, rather than focusing on solely on the financial profit.

The benefits Energy Communities can offer can be **environmental, social, and economic**.

Environmental benefits

- **Greenhouse Gas Reduction**, promoting the use of renewable energy sources, reducing carbon emissions and mitigating climate change.
- **Resource Efficiency**, encouraging efficient energy use, minimizing waste, and optimizing resource consumption.
- **Ecosystem Protection**, reducing the environmental impact of energy generation.
- **Shift towards cleaner energy sources**, leading to improved air and water quality within the community.
- **Contribution to sustainable development**, ensuring a balance between environmental preservation and human well-being.

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Social benefits

- **Community Empowerment**, involving citizens in local energy decisions.
- **Social cohesion**, fostering cooperation, collaboration, and a sense of community among members through shared energy goals.
- **Fair access to clean energy**, promoting social equity and inclusivity among diverse community members.
- **Knowledge sharing**, encouraging knowledge exchange, awareness, and education on energy matters within the community.
- **Enhancement of skills**, expertise, and capacity among community members, supporting sustainable development.

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Economic benefits

- **Reduced individual costs for participants**, due to the collective procurement and sharing of energy resources.
- **Growth of local energy businesses and start-ups**, fostering entrepreneurship and economic development.
- **Attraction of private investments in the clean energy transition**, stimulating economic growth and job creation.
- **Revenue generation from energy sales and service provided by the community**, contributing to the local economy.
- **Value retention within the community** rather than flowing to external corporations.

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Example of local benefits of an Energy Community

Energy communities help in developing local value-chains, jobs, and skills.

The Lyndoch residential community microgrid project, which interconnected over 30 homes via a tiered grid system was the first smart embedded residential rooftop microgrid in South Africa.

Green energy initiatives help to ensure the sustainability and longevity of projects. They also clearly demonstrate the value of enhancing citizen engagement in localised clean energy transitions.

[Lyndoch Community](#)

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Flexibility of smart energy transition

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Flexibility is key

Increased flexibility is a key technical property that has to be included in the solutions of smart energy transition. This is because smart energy transition:

- Increases weather-dependent production with constantly varying power.
- Decreases control power capacity due to run-down of fossil production.
- Decreases inertia of the grid leading to stability issues.

Consumers' flexibility is perceived as a promising way to balance the system.

- What does this mean for cooperatives?
- What are the means for increasing flexibility in energy communities?

[LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform – Guidance Hub](#)

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Flexibility is key

Interesting opportunity is that flexibility services may offer **significant possibilities to improve the financial view of an Energy Community**.

Members of Energy Community may get financial benefit for their flexible consumption of energy (demand-side flexibility).

Cooperatives and citizen energy communities may have an important role to play due to their ability to mobilise citizens beyond commercial offers.

[LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform – Guidance Hub](#) [FLEXCoop – Flexibility Services for Energy Cooperatives](#)

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Example solution of flexibility

In order to get familiar with flexibility possibilities of Energy Communities, the project **REScoopVPP** is also worth exploring.

The main aim of REScoopVPP is to set-up a community-driven virtual power plant that can actually provide **flexibility services to the grid** and contributes to a **100% share of renewable energy sources** into the grid.

The project aims to make existing buildings smarter from flexibility point of view. In addition, renewable energy cooperatives and Energy Communities can organise themselves as aggregators or retailers of renewable energy.

[LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform – Guidance Hub](#) [REScoopVPP](#)

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Flexibility in a large-scale Energy Community

The **biggest and technically most advanced Energy Community in Finland** exist in the municipality of Lempäälä, Southern Finland.

This technically advanced Energy Community has very **flexible energy system** combining power grid and district heating network, and it includes **MW-scale energy storages** (electric and thermal), **MW-scale solar electricity system**, **high-temperature fuel cells** and **gas engines**.

This large-scale Energy Community offers flexibility to Finnish electric energy system by **taking part in power balance control of the national grid**.

i Self-sufficient energy System LEMENE Microgrid

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Video 2: Overcoming barriers in Energy Communities

Overcoming barriers in Energy Communities

25 January 2024

Co-funded by the European Union

Introduction

2

Energy Communities are becoming more and more popular, since they provide one solution for the progress of smart energy transition.

In this Capacity Building Module, we provide **hints and best practices from other European initiatives**, as well as a wide range of **barriers** that would have to be taken into consideration when setting up an Energy Community.

For who?

Videos are targeted to any stakeholder interested in Energy Communities:

- **Municipalities** supporting the creation of Energy Communities
- **Ministries** and **Public authorities** at local, regional and national levels
- **Energy agencies** and **Energy companies**
- **Local associations**
- **Investors** and **Renewable energy developers**
- **Consultants**
- **Citizens**

4

5

Insiders and Outsiders

Different projects have **different objectives, target audiences and outcomes**, providing useful insights and best practices.

Target audience

By **Insiders** we mean actors who are already engaged in some Energy Community initiatives.

- High level of awareness / knowledgeable about the topics of Energy Community, self-consumption and bottom-up energy social energy initiatives.

Professionals in the energy sector, proactive and operative municipalities, already existing Energy Communities, SMEs operative in Energy Community projects...

Outsiders

Best practices

Insiders

Outsiders are potentially interested actors that are not yet engaged in Energy Communities. Their engagement can be direct (part of the EC) or indirect (support structure).

- Concerned about climate change and want to be part of energy transition. Partly equipped with the level of knowledge required.

Citizens, municipalities, associations (e.g., neighbourhoods), investors, distribution system operators (DSO), service providers, promoters, financing bodies...

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Insiders and Outsiders

How to turn Outsiders into Insiders?

- By **equipping** them with the **necessary knowledge**.
- By **inspiring** them with **existing use cases and success stories**.
- By **supplying** them the **instruments and the network** to become an Insider.

Insiders
(professionals, municipalities, already existing ECs, ...)

Outsiders
(citizens, municipalities, associations, investors, ...)

Best Practices

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Inspiration from other European Initiatives: LIGHTNESS

LIGHTNESS Engages stakeholders through national engagement plans, delivers regulatory guidelines for Citizen Energy Communities (CEC) implementation while implementing an innovative and multidimensional assessment methodology through digital twin integration.

<p>Outsiders</p>	<p>Citizens, building owners, policy makers and municipalities</p>		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Report on Environmentally just engagement • Energy Communities for Just Energy Transitions on a Local Scale • Analysis report on relevant smart energy services • Financing the CEC journey through traditional and disruptive mechanisms
		<p>Insiders</p>	<p>Energy cooperatives, aggregators, facility managers, policy makers, governments and municipalities</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Mapping of relevant stakeholders • PESTEL Analysis & benchmarking of CEC implementations

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Inspiration from other European Initiatives: DECIDE

Filtered 11 existing and heterogeneous Energy Communities and created a self-organised virtual environment, called Coffee Shop, to share best practises and lessons learned.

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Inspiration from other European Initiatives: UP-STAIRS

Creates flexible and iterative business model frameworks for One-Stop-Shops to accelerate creation of Energy Communities, support local stakeholders and test new energy service model frameworks.

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Inspiration from other European Initiatives: COME-RES

Aims at facilitating the market uptake of renewable energy sources in electricity sector. Covers diverse socio-technical systems including community PV, wind (onshore), storage and integrated community solutions.

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Inspiration from other European Initiatives: COME-RES

Aims at designing and implementing replicable and commercially viable services of Positive Energy Neighbourhoods in a set of three European urban contexts, and finally integrating these technologies and packages in different Living Labs.

Outsiders

Neighbourhood associations, policy makers, regulators, politicians, policy advisory organisations

Insiders

Stakeholders (citizens, industry, academia & government) for building up positive energy neighbourhoods, with a strong focus on living labs and innovators

- [Capacity Building Handbook](#) supporting institutions interested in setting up Living Labs working in the field of energy
- oPEN Lab Toolbox for policymakers and commercial actors to gather knowledge about the innovations and insights on how they can be supported/deployed in their region*
- oPEN Lab co-creation game – [Instructions & game board](#)

i oPEN Lab Project

*To be integrated in oPEN Lab website 13

Inspiration from other European Initiatives: COME-RES

Achieves island energy independence through renewable energy generation and storage, a demand response platform, and promoting user engagement in a local Energy Community.

Outsiders

Island Municipalities not currently involved with Energy Communities

Insiders

Island Energy Communities in the EU

- Innovative business models and exploitation plans
- Renewable energy resource assessment tools (multi-criteria decision analysis methods)
- Integrated and digitalised smart grid (cloud-based ICT solution)
- Demand response platform for community flexibility management
- Renewable energy resource assessment tools (multi-criteria decision analysis methods)
- Application (behaviour change nudging with consumption and production monitoring capabilities)

i REACT Project

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Overcoming barriers: best practices and tips

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Barriers hindering Energy Community initiatives

While setting up and working on Energy Communities there might be various barriers to overcome:

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Best practices for overcoming technical barriers

Distribution System Operator (DSO) involvement

- **Support** is needed, since DSOs have difficulties to include Energy Communities in their business models. Energy efficiency actions and Energy Communities are often quite complex and typically not cost effective from DSO point of view.
- **Sources, consumption targets** and **storages** of energy are often manifold in Energy Communities. This increases the complexity and interconnectivity of energy network, and **technical issues** easily arise.
- To improve DSO's **business opportunities**, minimum number of actors connected to Energy Community should be negotiated together with DSO. DSOs can be reluctant to provide strategic information, due to complexity and privacy requirements of the distribution systems. Possible risks are **low degree of predictability** and **control on energy demand**.
- **Protective measures** must be taken carefully into account when connection battery energy storages to power grid.

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Best practices for overcoming technical barriers

Data collection

- Data access and collection can be a hindering factor in development of an Energy Community. Privacy concerns have to be taken carefully into account, and creating trust between the community actors will be fundamentally important.
- To utilize the energy and power measurements of an Energy Community in full, proper monitoring devices and a necessary connection to transmit data to the data provider have to be accomplished.
- Development of project services may be hindered by the lack of available data. Some Energy Communities may also suffer from low level of internet connection, which decreases the quality of collected data.
- In some rural Energy Communities power quality requirements may be unclear.

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For technical barriers...remember:

- Design your technical offers based on functionality and user accessibility deploying project tools in real life poses various integration challenges.
- Check [technical catalogues](#) as a basis for your propositions.
- Invest in technical simplicity, since most Energy Communities would like to keep things as clear as possible. However, if interest towards sophisticated systems arise, AI can be strategically utilized for long term prediction of energy consumption and generation.
- Utilize available digital tools to support your decision-making
 - [Prosumer-Investment Calculator](#)
 - [Local RES Planning tool](#)
- Be very clear in terms of usage and storage.

Please note:
Not all identified tools are free to use and/or accessible to users with low technical knowledge level.
Technical offices could indeed use already existing tools to support citizens, limiting useless replications and avoiding duplication of efforts.

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Best practices for overcoming financial and operational barriers

- Since Energy Communities represents “a new player” in energy sector, **lack of established market** is a typical barrier. A market is required to allow for cooperation and interaction between different stakeholders in the energy system.
- Many technical models have been developed to integrate distributed energy sources in the grid. However, **more solutions are required** to integrate stakeholders in the decision-making of an Energy Community.
- **Governance barriers** may be confronted when many different actors are involved in **multi-carrier systems**. Profitable solution for all may be difficult to find when Energy Community includes for example many **DSOs** (electric, natural gas, district heating and cooling) and **big investments of renewable energy technologies**.
- It may often be unclear how individual members and local communities benefit more from the business models of Energy Communities than from the ones of traditional energy services.

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Best practices for overcoming financial and operational barriers

- In some cases, customers are asked to assume **grid expansion costs** related to Energy Community, although they do not necessarily get any financial benefits. Benefits may be related to power quality, which mainly benefit the grid company. As the solution, regulations should be defined in such a way that cost reductions in the grid should be passed to Energy Community.
- The reality of a given value proposition may often be **unclear** in Energy Communities. It is often difficult to assess if the given value proposition will work in practice, even if an extensive process of business modelling has given a positive result.
- Participants can **enter and leave** the Energy Community **risking its stability**. This is why clear decisions should be set on the conditions to access and leave the community during its lifetime.

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For financial and operational barriers...remember:

- Multi-Actor Multi-Criteria Analysis provides a successful methodology to integrate multiple stakeholders in the decision-making process.
- Consider feed-in tariffs, electricity prices and availability of local renewable energy providers when developing a business model framework.
- Start from and co-create with the users, enhancing their sense of belonging in the market and making clear how they are benefiting from it.

[MAMCA decision making tool](#)

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Best practices for overcoming participation and user engagement barriers

Low engagement level

- From day one, co-create the solution together and have constant communication with users. Experts in social sciences need to be utilized, energy retailers seldom fit to the role.
- Energy hubs bear potential engagement barriers for the final user. Business models might not be attractive enough or user interfaces are not easily accessible to everyone.
- Long-term engagement can be enhanced with face-to-face meetings.
- Organizing communal events is excellent in increasing engagement level. It is also found that partially funded actions (not 100%) can increase the sense of ownership.
- Aesthetic and environmental impacts are important.
- Social acceptance may be more important than technical details or business models

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Best practices for overcoming participation and user engagement barriers

Low level of knowledge

- It is important to realize that most citizens have low knowledge about energy transition and lack of confidence related to monitoring installation. It is unlikely that such citizens would take the role of active prosumers. The best practice is to include citizens from day 1 to the project.
- Low awareness of the benefits of Energy Communities creates barriers.
- Technical benefits of Energy Communities are not enough to remove barriers. Highlighting financial, environmental and community benefits increase positive reception.
- Capacity building in local municipalities is important. It can be promoted by means of access to improved and more accessible data and knowledge.

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For participation and user engagement barriers...remember:

- Co-create the solution together and have constant communication with users.
- Build strong connection with local actors.
- Be realistic with expected outcomes.
- Use accessible language.
- Let them build their own scenario.
- Prioritize face-to-face interactions as much as possible.

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Best practices for overcoming legal and regulatory barriers

Transposition in the national contexts and enabling frameworks

- **Each country** of the European Union, although supported by European guidelines and framework, has its **own legislative basis** for regulation of Energy Communities.
- In some countries the regulation of Energy Communities is **unclear or non-existent**. This is one factor lowering the interest and engagement level of people (both users and promoters) towards Energy Communities.
- The **varieties of legal forms** of Energy Communities offer different frameworks and opportunities in terms of decision-making, liability, tax advantages, start-up costs, or administrative burdens
- A **proper study of Energy Community regulations** in different countries of the European Union should be thoroughly conducted to clarify the situation.

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Best practices for overcoming participation and user engagement barriers

Distribution System Operator (DSO)

- Interest of all stakeholders needs to be considered while developing regulations of Energy Communities. DSOs have duties that need to remain cost effective.
- Even if all the legal and regulatory conditions are met, local opposition can take place, especially for remote locations, mainly due to cost efficiency.
- To resolve pragmatic issues emerging from regulation DSO support is needed. This is important when an Energy Community has its own separate microgrid that is connected to the national grid.
- Bear in mind that the minimum bid size to participate in flexibility services may be difficult to address for small Energy Communities.

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For legal and regulatory barriers...remember:

- **Community energy actors** should play a crucial role in supporting national governments to put in place an enabling legal framework that promotes and facilitates the development of renewable Energy Communities.
- The [SCORE Transposition Guidance for citizen energy policies](#) provides useful recommendations to be applied when drafting national legislation and regulation.
- **Policy advocacy strategies** and **consultation activities** with national governments to assess what is holding back public and community ownership are crucial.

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Video 3: Stakeholder engagement in Energy Communities

Stakeholder engagement
in Energy Communities

LIFE-BECKON

Co-funded by the
European Union

26 January 2024

Introduction

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2

Energy Communities are becoming more and more popular, since they provide one solution for the progress of smart energy transition.

In this Capacity Building Module, we provide guidelines that you can take into account when for **engaging with stakeholders, involving citizens, and designing your communication strategies** throughout your Energy Community journey.

LIFE-BECKON

3

For who?

Videos are targeted to any stakeholder interested in Energy Communities:

- **Municipalities** supporting the creation of Energy Communities
- **Ministries and Public authorities** at local, regional and national levels
- **Energy agencies and Energy companies**
- **Local associations**
- **Investors and Renewable energy developers**
- **Consultants**
- **Citizens**

4

Stakeholders and Energy Community Actors

5

What is a stakeholder?

Stakeholders are **individuals, entities or organizations** that are:

- **Involved** and/or **interested** in a particular project or action (e.g., the set up or the support of an Energy Community in their city)
- **Affected** in some way by this project/action

The **input** the stakeholders can provide has a **direct impact** on the project's/action's upshot.

Stakeholders can also be referred to as Energy Community Actors and refer to the **individuals, entities or organizations** involved in any of the stages of an Energy Community (e.g., initiation, design, implementation and operation).

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Energy Community actors

Stakeholders in an Energy Community can be divided in 2 categories

Outsiders

By **Insiders** we mean actors who are already engaged in some Energy Community initiatives.

- High level of awareness / knowledgeable about the topics of Energy Community, self-consumption and bottom-up energy social energy initiatives.

Professionals in the energy sector, proactive and operative municipalities, already existing Energy Communities, SMEs operative in Energy Community projects...

Insiders

Outsiders are potentially interested actors that are not yet engaged in Energy Communities. Their engagement can be direct (part of the EC) or indirect (support structure).

- Concerned about climate change and want to be part of energy transition. Partly equipped with the level of knowledge required.

Citizens, municipalities, associations (e.g., neighbourhoods), investors, distribution system operators (DSO), service providers, promoters, financing bodies...

A stakeholder engagement plan should be tailored to each type of stakeholder, and at making outsiders into insiders.

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Who are my Stakeholders or Energy Community Actors?

Stakeholder can be any individual, entity or organisation that is directly or indirectly relevant to the Energy Community, and that is an insider or an outsider at any point from initiation to operation.

Civil Society Citizens, Households, environmental / community groups, NGOs, Trade/professional unions...

Government & Public Sector Local Authorities, Municipal departments (e.g., Energy), Central government, policy makers...

Academia & Universities University Departments (e.g., Planning/Energy), researchers, institutes...

Industry & Business Energy agencies, Distribution System Operators (DSOs), investors, entrepreneurs, SMEs, consultants...

These actors collaborate and interact within the Energy Community framework, each contributing their expertise, resources, and support to achieve the community's goals of sustainable and locally-driven energy initiatives. It is important to note that these actors can be a part of the Energy Community, or they can be a service provider to an Energy Community.

[Structured overview on optimized energy-efficiency interventions for Energy Communities and collective action](#)

8

Examples of key stakeholders to consider during your Energy Community journey

Civil Society		Government & Public Sector		Academia & Universities
Individuals and Households	Environmental and Community Groups*	Local Authorities and Municipalities	Policy Makers and Regulators	Research and Educational Institutions*
People who actively participate in the Energy Community, either as consumers or prosumers (those who both consume and generate energy).	Non-profit organizations and community groups with an interest in environmental sustainability and community well-being, actively participating in or supporting Energy Community initiatives.	People who actively participate in the Energy Community, either as consumers or prosumers (those who both consume and generate energy).	Government bodies and agencies that establish policies, regulations, and frameworks affecting the formation and operation of Energy Communities.	Universities, research organizations, and educational institutions that contribute to the knowledge, research, and training aspects of Energy Communities.

Insiders

Outsiders

*Can be an insider (as prosumer) or an outsider (as service provider) 9

Examples of key stakeholders to consider during your Energy Community journey

Industry & Business

Insiders
Outsiders

*Can be an insider (as prosumer) or an outsider (as service provider) 10

Why citizens are important stakeholders?

Citizens constitute an **essential stakeholder** when setting up Energy Communities, impacting the **success** and **effectiveness** of community's energy projects.

Align the community's projects with real local needs

Secure people's long-term support to the community, as they develop a sense of ownership on it

Boost innovation and creativity bringing fresh ideas and solutions from the people living in the community

Ensure social acceptance

Empower people to make informed decision about energy

Ensure transparency and accountability in decision-making and operations of the community

Stimulate economic benefits for the people (e.g., job creation within the community)

[Co-creation with Citizens: A guide to inspiring European, municipal co-creating policy and projects with citizens.](#)

11

Stakeholder engagement

Stakeholder engagement is about transposing your strategy, your operational plans and activities planned for the EC you will work for into the **who** you need to involve.

It is important to understand from the very beginning who are the relevant stakeholders for the Energy Community, defining what is the **added value** for them to be part of this community, and what is the **role** they should have in the different activities.

In addition, it is important to understand the **level of involvement expected** from the stakeholders to be able to design a communication strategy aligned with the expectations.

12

Guiding questions for stakeholder engagement

What will we do for whom and why?

Which problem are we trying to solve?

Which specific categories/sub-categories of people do we need?

What is the role of the targeted stakeholders?

Which are the actions we expect them to perform?

How and where do we recruit them?

How are we going to keep them engaged and supported throughout the process?

What are the relevant rewards for them?

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Stakeholder engagement when setting up an Energy Community

- Initiation**
 Founding members of the Energy Community, potential local partners, and individuals or groups interested in the project's objectives...
 Engagement: provide input to shape the community's vision and align its objectives with real needs and expectations
- Design**
 Local authorities, potential investors, suppliers, and community members...
 Engagement: Active involvement in the development of the business plan and the project design
- Implementation**
 Local authorities, regulatory bodies, community members, contractors, and technology providers...
 Engagement: Engaging with local authorities and regulatory for obtaining necessary permits and approvals, and training for community members regarding the Energy Community's constitution
- Operation**
 Community members, local authorities, and relevant partners or suppliers...
 Engagement: Ongoing engagement for the establishment of a proper organizational and management structure and the identification of new growth opportunities and expansion strategies

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Stakeholder engagement tools

There are various available toolboxes offering a wide range of tools and templates that can be used when engaging and co-creating with stakeholders

[LIFE-BECKON
OSS Platform –
Guidance Hub](#)

[UNaLab](#)

[SCORE
co-create
your city](#)

[DesignKit](#)

[Siscode](#)

[Life Loop](#)

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When engaging with stakeholders remember:

- **Manage expectations:** if your stakeholders are not open or positive to the idea of an Energy Community or a specific energy project, try to shift them to a positive mindset. Try to explain what are the benefits and added value for them to be part of this community. Define with clarity your scope and limitations from the very beginning
- **Talk their language:** it is important to provide a clear understanding to your stakeholders. Avoid technical/project terminologies that are difficult to understand or require technical knowledge. Use simple words and concrete examples to make your points
- **Sustain your stakeholders' interest in the long-run:** think your stakeholders in a sustainable way, thinking about the future of your community. Engage them wisely, in the right moments, and avoid overloading them with information that might decrease their interest/willingness to be part of the community.

i [DECIDE Stakeholder Engagement Guidebook](#) [COMPILE Stakeholder Engagement Guide](#)

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Communication strategies

Effective stakeholder management comes with **continuous communication** with your stakeholders. Developing **effective communication strategies**, you can ensure that your stakeholders will be **well-informed, actively engaged, and supporting** of the community and its projects

A **comprehensive approach** to communication is needed, taking into account the **different needs and expectations** of the different stakeholders.

i [RESCOOP EU Communications guide: Community energy communications at the local level](#)
[RESCOOP EU Best Practice Guide for Southeast Europe](#)
[RESCOOP EU Communications guide: Community energy communications at the local level](#)

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Communication strategies

When building your communication strategies, it is important to define:

- **Communication objectives**
 - Be clear on the goals you want to achieve with and for your stakeholders
 - Be realistic
 - Plan step-by-step: objectives and goals might change over time
- **Capacities and resources**
 - Think of knowledge and expertise you have in communication
 - Evaluate your resources (human, budget) needed to deliver your strategies
- **Target groups**
 - Different stakeholders might need different approaches when communicating with them: all-fit-on one solution is hard to be successful

i [Community Energy Municipal Guide](#)
[Guidelines to optimize energy-efficiency information campaigns and citizen participation](#)

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Communication strategies

- **Activities with/for your stakeholders**
 - Assess, based on your objectives, resources, and target groups, the types of activities you can perform (workshops, public consultations, webinars, info days, open discussions...)
 - Take into account different modalities for the activities (online, face-to-face, hybrid)
 - Choose carefully the frequency of the activities and communications with the stakeholders
 - Different target groups might need different types of activities, modalities, of optimal frequency for communication. Take that into account!
- **Convey clear messages**
 - Make sure to persuasively explain the vision of the Energy Community
 - Provide enough details to your stakeholders to understand the benefits of the Energy Community and the value for the to be part of it
 - Give context and meaning to your messages, so the stakeholders can relate

i [Community Energy Municipal Guide](#)
[Guidelines to optimize energy-efficiency information campaigns and citizen participation](#)

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When communicating with your stakeholders remember to:

- **Be adaptable:** Be prepared to adapt your communication strategies as the project progresses and as stakeholder needs change. Flexibility is key!
- **Make communication accessible:** Take into account potential language barriers and disabilities, ensuring to develop inclusive strategies. Everyone should be able participate in the dialogue
- **Be open and honest:** Transparency builds trust and fosters positive relationships with stakeholders. Share both successes and setbacks with them
- **Aim for two-way communication:** Establish mechanisms for feedback and input from your stakeholders. Be present, actively listening to their concerns, questions, and suggestions, and responding promptly to them

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Video 4: Governance models and legal structures of Energy Communities

Governance models and legal structures for Energy Communities

26 January 2024

Co-funded by the European Union

Introduction

2

Energy Communities are becoming more and more popular, since they provide one solution for the progress of smart energy transition.

In this Capacity Building Module, we explore why **governance is important** for Energy Communities, what are **potential governance and legal structures** that could be adopted, as well as key **guiding principles** for when choosing and building a governance model for an Energy Community.

3

For who?

Videos are targeted to any stakeholder interested in Energy Communities:

- **Municipalities** supporting the creation of Energy Communities
- **Ministries and Public authorities** at local, regional and national levels
- **Energy agencies and Energy companies**
- **Local associations**
- **Investors and Renewable energy developers**
- **Consultants**
- **Citizens**

4

Why governance matters in Energy Communities?

5

Why is governance important?

Governance is crucial for the Energy Communities, in terms of structure and management of the entity, fair decision making as well as community engagement.

Governance matters for:

- **Project success** - Ensures the efficient use of resources, accountability, and reaching project goals.
- **Community trust** - A transparent and representative governance model fosters trust among community members, ensuring their continuous involvement.
- **Resource management** - Ensures that energy and financial resources are used efficiently and responsibly.

It is crucial for the Energy Communities to strive **for transparent governance models** with clear **organizational structure**.

6

Building the governance model: first steps

EUCENA Best Practice Guide for Southeast Europe

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Building the governance model: first steps

- The **core group** of an Energy Community typically consists of **4-15 (or more) members**.
- For ensuring a transparent governance model with clear structure, a **strong, united core group** is needed.
- Understanding **individual motivations** helps in **task distribution** among the core group members.
- A **vision board** can help consolidate and explore collective ideas of the core group.
- Key questions for the core group:
 - **Who** are we?
 - What's our **collective goal**?
 - Which **resources** do we possess (technical, financial, social, political)?
 - What **challenges** might we face?
 - Which **activities** and projects do we want to create?

8

Factors influencing governance choices

There are factors that might **influence the choices** when building your governance model. These factors can be:

- **Size and scale** - Larger projects might require more structured, possibly public-led approaches, while smaller ones can be more grassroots.
- **Financial considerations** - Source of funding (public grants, private investments, community crowdfunding) can influence governance.
- **Regulations** - Local and national regulations might favor one model over the other, or even dictate specific governance structures.

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Legal structures

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Legal context

With the [Clean Energy for all Europeans package](#), European Commission introduced two definitions of an Energy Community:

- Renewable Energy Community (REC)
- Citizen Energy Community (CEC)

Please note:
This is the situation in 2024. Always check the current state of the legislation.

[Clean Energy for all Europeans package](#) [Rural Energy Community Advisory Hub](#)

For more details, check the Capacity Building Module on "Definition and benefits of Energy Communities"

11

Organizational structure and ownership

From a governance point of view, there are many similarities in the legal framework of both types of Energy Communities, as they both:

- Require a legal entity as a **community umbrella**.
- Require a **specific governance**.
- Must be **voluntary** and **open**.
- Should be **value driven** rather than merely focusing on financial profits.

[COMPILE Toolkit: Stakeholder Engagement Guide](#) [JRC Energy Communities: an overview of energy and social innovation](#)

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Organizational structure and ownership

There are various organizational structures that enable citizens to participate in and collectively own renewable energy, forming the basis for the establishment of an Energy Community. These include:

- **Cooperative**
- **Community trust and foundation**
- **Associations**
- **Limited Partnership**
- **Public-Private Partnership**
- **Non-profit customer owned company**

Important to note that these do not define directly governance models but set conditions and requirements for how and who can be allowed in the community.

[JRC Energy Communities: an overview of energy and social innovation](#)

For more details, check the Capacity Building Module on "Regulatory highlights for Energy Communities"

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Cooperative

The most common legal entity for Energy Communities. Example energy cooperatives represent the prevailing and rapidly expanding model within Energy Communities. In this form of ownership, the primary beneficiaries are the cooperative's members. It enjoys popularity in countries where renewable energy and community-based energy initiatives have made significant strides.

Som Energia in Spain, founded in 2010. At Som Energia, you pay a deposit to become a member. After that, you have the right to buy renewable energy produced from existing sources. The opportunity to participate financially in these investment projects.

[JRC Energy Communities: an overview of energy and social innovation](#) [Som Energia](#)

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Community trust and foundation

Community trusts and foundations focus on **creating social value** and **promoting local development**, rather than prioritizing individual benefits. The profits generated by these entities are **utilized for the benefit of the entire community**, even when individual citizens may not have the resources to invest in specific projects. Essentially, they **operate as for-the-public-good companies**.

The Isle of Eigg, Scotland, founded in 2008. The Isle of Eigg electrification scheme was a community-inspired project to electrify the whole island and was the biggest project of their first ten-year plan for the sustainable development of the island. The electricity system is entirely stand-alone, has no external input from a mainland utility, and is operated and maintained for the community by Eigg Electric Ltd., a wholly-owned subsidiary of the Isle of Eigg Heritage Trust.

[JRC Energy Communities: an overview of energy and social innovation](#) [The Isle of Eigg](#)

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Associations

Example housing associations are **non-profit organizations** that play a crucial role in social housing. These associations are particularly well-suited for **addressing energy poverty** and **ensuring that residents have access to safe and affordable housing**. The members or the tenants of the social housing estate are responsible for managing the estate. The housing association can be found as example in UK, Denmark or Sweden.

Bostadsrättsföreningen Lyckansberg, Sweden. A housing association with 85 tenants in Sweden, has been producing and managing green energy autonomously for since 2018. The association's solar cell plant generates electricity for common purposes, such as lighting, laundry cabins, sauna, and other functions in the association hall. In case of surplus, PV electricity is sold online, and in case of higher demand, electricity is bought from the grid.

JRC Energy Communities: an overview of energy and social innovation [Bostadsrättsföreningen Lyckansberg](#)

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Limited partnerships

Limited partnerships involve individuals collaborating to **distribute responsibilities** and **generate profits** within the context of community energy. In such arrangements, **governance typically hinges on the value of each partner's share**, rather than adhering strictly to a one-member-one-vote principle.

Sprakebüll is a pioneering Energy Community in Germany that was first founded in 1998. The project adopted the GmbH & Co. KG model, which is a hybrid of the legal forms limited liability company (GmbH) and limited partnership (KG). Sprakebüll started with a group of villagers who were pioneers in community wind farming. Over the years, they have built up more wind power, as well as solar power and a biogas plant-based district heating system.

JRC Energy Communities: an overview of energy and social innovation [Sprakebüll](#)

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Public-private partnerships

Public-private partnerships (PPPs) involve **collaborations between local authorities, citizen groups, and businesses**. These partnerships are established to **ensure energy provision and other community benefits**. By working together, these entities create a **more sustainable and inclusive environment for the community**.

Duurzaam Ameland in The Netherlands, founded in 2007. The island of Ameland is known for its sustainable electricity and heat production projects with several projects implemented with partner companies.

JRC Energy Communities: an overview of energy and social innovation [Duurzaam Ameland](#)

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Non-profit customer-owned enterprises

Non-profit customer-owned enterprises are **legal structures** employed by communities to manage **independent grid networks**. These entities are **particularly well-suited for community district heating networks**, which are prevalent in Nordic countries. In such networks, the focus is on **community ownership** and **sustainable energy solutions**.

Marstal Fjernvarme is a solar district heating plant located on the island of Ærø, Denmark. It was founded as a cooperative limited company A.m.b.A. and has been owned by the inhabitants of Marstal since the 1960s. The company operates on a not-for-profit ownership model, where profits are returned to the members in the form of lower energy prices.

[JRC Energy Communities: an overview of energy and social innovation](#) [Marstal Fjernvarme](#) [Marstal Fjernvarme district](#)

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Building Governance

20

Institutional construction: Key Roles

The Member

- Individuals or legal entities.
- Municipalities, enterprises*, and individuals are allowed by the European law to be members.
- Membership entails rights and responsibilities, including participation in governance and potential mandatory contributions.

The General Assembly (GA)

- The GA is the primary decision-making body.
- Comprises all members and sets the cooperative's main strategy.

[COMPILE Toolkit: Stakeholder Engagement Guide](#)

*Only small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are allowed in REC. 21

Institutional construction: Key Roles

The Board of Directors

- Implements the GA's strategy.
- Members should have equal access or representation.
- Board composition and conflict of interest rules are defined in the cooperative's statutes.

Advisory Boards and Supporting Bodies

- Provide advice without decision-making power.
- Examples include diversity boards, technical boards, employee representation, and stakeholder representation boards.

COMPILE Toolkit: Stakeholder Engagement Guide

*Only small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) are allowed in REC. 22

Governance building principle 1: Open and Voluntary Membership

Open Membership

- Energy Communities should **avoid** arbitrary or **discriminatory criteria** for membership.
- Criteria should align with **community objectives**, like minimum investment thresholds or membership dues.
- Membership openness varies based on community activity:
 - For **renewables projects**, membership might close after raising necessary finance.
 - For **energy sharing or district heating**, eligibility might be tied to geographical or technical limitations.
 - For **other services (e.g., EV charging)**, communities should remain open to all potential consumers.
- Emphasis on **ensuring diversity**, addressing socio-economic issues, promoting gender and racial equality, and supporting households with limited income.

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Governance building principle 1: Open and Voluntary Membership

Voluntary Membership

- Two potential relationships: **member/investor** and **business-customer**.
 - **Member/investor** relationship involves rights (e.g., **limited ROI, transparency, decision-making**) and responsibilities (e.g., **volunteering time, voting, resource contribution**).
 - **Business-customer** relationship ensures consumers' rights, including the **right to switch suppliers**. No one can be forced to join or remain in an Energy Community.

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Governance building principle 2: *Democratic member control*

Energy Communities are controlled by members who actively participate in policy direction and decision-making.

The governance models aims at supporting the **community's autonomy** and the **collective interest** of all members.

Voting rights ensure equal decision-making power for all members, typically through the **one-member-one-vote principle**.

Accountability

- Statutes ensure that management and elected board representatives are accountable to the members, typically represented in the general assembly.

 [COMPILE Toolkit: Stakeholder Engagement Guide](#)

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Governance building principle 2: *Democratic member control*

Representation and Diversity

- Ensures different groups within the community (e.g., **employees, clients, financial contributors**) are adequately represented.
- Energy Communities unite citizens, enterprises of all sizes, and municipalities.
- It's vital to ensure **no group feels disenfranchised** and that each group has adequate representation in decision-making bodies.
- Mechanisms like **veto rights** for minority members or **weighted voting** can be implemented for fair representation.

 [COMPILE Toolkit: Stakeholder Engagement Guide](#)

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Governance building principle 3: *Member economic participation*

Membership Contribution

- To join an Energy Community, individuals typically **contribute to its capital**.
- For certain activities, like energy sharing, participation can be through **providing resources**, such as self-produced renewable electricity.

Rights and benefits

- Through their contributions, members gain **rights to a return on their investment** and **decision-making rights** concerning the community's policies and operations.

Incentives for Participation

- While some Energy Communities offer services to non-members, many **incentivize membership**.
- Common incentives include **discounts on energy bills** for households that choose to become members.

 [COMPILE Toolkit: Stakeholder Engagement Guide](#)

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Governance building principle 4: *Autonomy and independence*

Autonomy ensures the community is **jointly owned and controlled by its members, not dominated by a single or small group of members.**

Autonomy also supports democratic internal decision-making, ensuring **all members are represented, irrespective of their investment size.**

Business partnerships with traditional market actors shouldn't compromise the **community's decision-making independence.**

 [COMPILE Toolkit: Stakeholder Engagement Guide](#)

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Governance building principle 4: *Autonomy and independence*

Autonomy can be reflected in an Energy Community's statutes in many ways:

- **Limit the capital held by one member or group** to safeguard collective autonomy.
- **Place restrictions on the withdrawal or liquidation of investments** by members to ensure community stability.
- **Impose duties on the board** for financial autonomy, sustainability, and refraining from speculative actions.
- **Restrict seeking certain sources of capital**, like institutional investors or larger energy companies.
- **Limit external financing** that could compromise autonomy.
- **Implement democratic decision-making** based on the one-person-one-vote principle, ensuring equal treatment of members.

 [COMPILE Toolkit: Stakeholder Engagement Guide](#)

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Governance building principle 5: *Education, Training, and Information*

Communities prioritize educating and training members, representatives, managers, employees, and the local public.

For Energy Communities, this extends to providing advice on energy-saving actions, financing options, and promoting an energy-efficient lifestyle.

Impact on Energy Communities

- Focus on **offering targeted advice** on energy consumption reduction and securing financing for energy-saving activities.
- Training and education aim to enlighten the local community on energy matters, guiding them towards **energy-conscious living.**
- Such educational initiatives are often **central to the Energy Community's main objectives.**

 [COMPILE Toolkit: Stakeholder Engagement Guide](#)

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Governance building principle 6: Cooperation between Energy Communities

Cooperation is vital for the success of Energy Community initiatives, especially for new communities lacking experience. Experienced Energy Communities serve as valuable resources, offering information, technical expertise, and support.

Informal and Formal Assistance

- Many established Energy Communities assist newer ones informally.
- Some have specific objectives to help initiate new Energy Communities.

Historical Context

- Cooperation among Energy Communities led to the formation of REScoop.eu, the European Federation of Citizen Energy Cooperatives.
- Originated from communities exchanging best practices and challenges.
- This collaboration expanded into a European project, uniting energy cooperatives from various EU Member States, eventually forming REScoop.EU.

 [COMPILE Toolkit: Stakeholder Engagement Guide](#)

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Governance building principle 7: Concern for community

Energy Communities are distinguished by their objectives, focusing on addressing local socio-economic concerns and ensuring a **democratic** and **inclusive energy transition**. Their unique approach justifies **special policy support from the EU**.

EU Law Perspective

- Energy Communities **must prioritize environmental, economic, or social benefits over financial profits**.
- Profits can be made but should **be reinvested into community activities or used for public interest aims**.

Value Proposition

- Energy Communities can **generate revenue for socially innovative purposes**.
- **Financial** benefits to members are **secondary to the broader community aims**.

 [COMPILE Toolkit: Stakeholder Engagement Guide](#)

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Governance building principle 7: Concern for community

Beneficiary Groups

- Benefits can be aimed at shareholders/members or the broader local community.

Potential Benefits

- **Local development** promotion.
- **Public infrastructure** investment.
- **Reduced energy bills** for households.
- **Increased local renewable energy production**.
- **Greenhouse gas emission reductions**.
- **Various services provision** to members.
- **Investments** in energy efficiency, addressing energy poverty, and ensuring member solidarity.
- **Education and training** initiatives.
- **Promotion of energy democracy and citizen empowerment**.

 [COMPILE Toolkit: Stakeholder Engagement Guide](#)

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Real-life examples

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Real-life examples

Through the exploration of these real-life cases, our objective is to **vividly illustrate the diverse governance models** that have been strategically adopted for various types of Energy Communities.

By delving into these **practical examples**, we aim to provide a **comprehensive understanding of the nuanced decision-making structures and frameworks** that underpin the functioning of Energy Communities across different contexts.

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ESEK: A Biomass Energy Community in Greece

ESEK stands for Energy Community of Karditsa, a **cooperative** that produces and distributes energy from biomass and solar sources.

Biomass Plant - ESEK operates a plant that converts wood waste into solid biofuels for heating and cooling purposes. The plant uses local biomass suppliers and transporters, creating jobs and income for the community.

Solidarity Solar Project - ESEK's next goal is to install solar panels on the roofs of its members, using virtual net metering and net metering schemes. This project will reduce the electricity bills of the members and support the transition to renewable energy.

Decision Making Roles and Gender - ESEK has 385 members, mostly men, who represent their households. ESEK also has some SMEs and municipalities as members. ESEK has a board of directors (9 persons) and a supervisory board (2 persons), elected by the members every 2 years. Each member has one vote, regardless of the number of shares they own. ESEK holds a general assembly every year, where all members are equal.

EUCENA Best Practice Guide for Southeast Europe [ESEK](#)

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WEnCoop in Greece

WEnCoop, Greece’s pioneering all-female Energy Community, was founded by the **Greek Association of Women Entrepreneurs**.

Solar Park and National Participation - WEnCoop has successfully completed a 1 MWp solar park, contributing clean energy to the grid. A second 1 MWp solar park is in the planning phase, further enhancing their impact. WEnCoop’s choice to sell energy directly to the grid (rather than net metering) enables national participation. Members, scattered across Greece, collectively contribute to the energy transition.

Inclusivity and Expertise - WEnCoop aims to demonstrate that even members without specialized energy expertise can actively participate in the transition. The heart of WEnCoop lies in its female entrepreneurs, all members of the Greek Association of Women Entrepreneurs. To join WEnCoop, one must demonstrate a link to female entrepreneurship and be a member of the Association.

Decision-Making Structure - WEnCoop has a Board of Directors, that is responsible for strategic decisions, a General Assembly that ensures equal participation and collective decision-making, and an Oversight Board, that provides guidance and accountability.

[EUCENA Best Practice Guide for Southeast Europe](#) [WEnCoop](#)

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Elektropionir: Empowering Serbia’s Energy Transition

Elektropionir, established in December 2019, is a Serbian Energy Community driven by enthusiasts passionate about renewable energy and innovative civic organization organized as a cooperative.

Mission and Principles - Elektropionir aims to actively involve and empower citizens in Serbia’s energy transition. Sustainable electricity production is also a primary goal; Elektropionir demonstrates that environmentally and economically sustainable electricity generation is achievable under cooperative principles.

Decision-Making structure - In Elektropionir decisions are made democratically, following the principle of one member, one vote. Female directors (both founding and current) play key roles, including the female chair of the Assembly.

Key Stakeholders and Partnerships – the Serbian Ministry of Mining and Energy) and Serbian Distribution System Operator are key stakeholders for Elektropionir, while Energy Cooperatives, Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Serbia, Solar PV Project Developers, Consumer Protection Organizations, Informally Organized Prosumers and Green NGOs are important allies.

[EUCENA Best Practice Guide for Southeast Europe](#) [Elektropionir](#)

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Need more examples?

Find examples of Energy Communities from all over Europe:

[Energy Community Platform](#)

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Video 5: Regulation highlights for Energy Communities

Regulation highlights for
Energy Communities

26 January 2024

LIFE-BECKON

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European Union

Introduction

2

Energy Communities are becoming more and more popular, since they provide one solution for the progress of smart energy transition.

This Capacity Building Module aims to assist emerging Energy Communities in navigating **regulatory challenges**. It explores the **EU's regulatory landscape** for Energy Communities and provides strategies for **accessing regulatory frameworks, policies, and support mechanisms** at national, regional, and local levels. Additionally, it emphasizes the crucial **role of stakeholders** in shaping regulatory frameworks conducive to Energy Community development.

3

For who?

Videos are targeted to any stakeholder interested in Energy Communities:

- **Municipalities** supporting the creation of Energy Communities
- **Ministries and Public authorities** at local, regional and national levels
- **Energy agencies and Energy companies**
- **Local associations**
- **Investors and Renewable energy developers**
- **Consultants**
- **Citizens**

4

European Regulatory Foundation

5

EU's regulatory framework on Energy Communities

The Clean Energy for All Europeans Package (CEP): Adopted in May 2019, the CEP provides a legal framework aimed at helping the EU achieve its 2030 climate and energy objectives. It formally recognizes Energy Communities as pivotal players in the transition of the energy system, signifying a shift in the role of citizens from being passive consumers to active participants.

the key legislative acts defining Energy Communities are:

1. Directive (EU) 2018/2001 (Recast Renewable Energy Directive): Commonly referred to as "RED II", this directive was required to be implemented by June 2021.
2. Directive (EU) 2019/944 (Recast Electricity Directive): Also known as the "Internal Electricity Market Directive (IEMD)", its implementation was mandated by December 2020.

 [LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform – Guidance Hub](#)

6

Energy Communities in Legislative Acts

With the [Clean Energy for all Europeans package](#) European Commission introduced two definitions of an Energy Community:

- Renewable Energy Community (REC)
- Citizen Energy Community (CEC)

*Please note:
This is the situation in 2024. Always check the current state of the legislation.*

i [Clean Energy for all Europeans package](#) [Rural Energy Community Advisory Hub](#)

For more details, check the Capacity Building Module on "Definition and Benefits of Energy Communities"

7

Stages of implementation of EU Directives

Understanding the regulatory process of implementing EU directives is essential for Energy Communities. Overall, this knowledge empowers Energy Communities to navigate the legal landscape, access support, make informed decisions, advocate for their interests, and collaborate effectively to achieve common goals. The regulatory process of implementing EU directives involves three main stages:

i [LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform – Guidance Hub](#)
[COME-RES: Implementing EU Provisions for Enabling Frameworks for RECs in nine countries: Progress, Delays, and Gaps](#)

8

Role of Key Actors in the Energy Communities (ECs):

A multitude of significant actors are involved in establishing framework conditions for ECs and play crucial roles throughout the lifespan of such initiatives. These key actors encompass a diverse range of stakeholders engaged in shaping and supporting the development of Energy Communities.

i [LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform – Guidance Hub](#)

*DSO: Distribution System Operators
TSO: Transmission System Operators
ESCO: Energy Service Companies*

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Up-to-date Information on EC Regulatory: Key Resources

European Union and European Commission

EUR-Lex

EUR-Lex is the official database for EU law, housing all EU directives, regulations, and decisions. It's an essential resource for accessing original legislative texts.

[Link](#)

This initiative by the European Commission aids local actors, including citizens, local authorities, and businesses, in initiating and enhancing clean energy projects led by Energy Communities across European urban areas.

[Link](#)

THE
RURAL ENERGY
COMMUNITY
ADVISORY HUB

Empower the development of sustainable energy community projects in European rural areas by supporting citizens and authorities to set up and maintain Energy Communities.

[Link](#)

REScoop.EU

REScoop.eu stands as the European federation for citizen energy cooperatives.

[Link 1](#)

[Link 2](#)

[LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform – Guidance Hub](#)

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Detailed Transposition into National Legislation

11

National implementation of directives

This section examines the process of transposing EU directives into national legislation across member states. It explores the key aspects that need to be monitored and studied to ensure effective implementation and alignment with EU regulations.

Transposition of REC and CEC definitions

Key aspects include the integration and coherence of REC/CEC definitions, adherence to EU criteria, clarity of purpose, incorporation of cooperative governance principles, provision for legal entities, citizen participation, establishment of oversight mechanisms, and the number of definitions present.

Enabling framework and support schemes

Key aspects include assessing obstacles and development potential, removing regulatory barriers, defining DSO duties, ensuring fair registration and licensing procedures, providing incentives based on Cost-Benefit Analysis, ensuring non-discriminatory treatment, enhancing accessibility for low-income households, providing tools for accessing finance and information, building regulatory capacity for public authorities, and reporting on enabling frameworks in National Energy and Climate Plans. Additionally, the adaptation of support schemes to facilitate EC development is emphasized.

[LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform – Guidance Hub](#)
[REScoop Transposition Tracker](#)

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Follow Transposition in each EU-country

Transposition Tracker Definitions of RECs and CECs

The Transposition tracker monitors REC and CEC definitions across EU countries. It provides a map and country tables showing progress and a separate tab for support schemes. Detailed assessments sourced from legislative texts are available by clicking on a country. [Link](#)

LIFE-BECKON [LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform – Guidance Hub](#)

Financing Tracker Recovery and Resilience fund

Evaluates Member States' use of EU public funds to support Energy Communities in line with REC provisions. It identifies nations with robust national frameworks for EC despite not utilizing EU funds. It serves as an advocacy tool and roadmap for policymakers. [Link](#)

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Up-to-date Information on EC Regulatory: Key Resources

National Regulatory Authorities in the Field of Energy and Constructions

National Regulatory Authorities (NRAs) play a crucial role in overseeing the energy markets of individual European countries, ensuring that they align with EU regulatory policies and meet set targets. These bodies work in tandem with ministries focused on energy and construction to streamline and regulate the energy sector. To get a comprehensive list of NRAs for various European countries, visit the official EU page: [Find National Regulatory Authority](#).

Examples from LIFE-BECKON demo sites:

Комисия за енергийно и водно регулиране
Energy and Water Regulatory Commission

Energitilsynet
Energy Regulatory Authority

Comisión nacional de los mercados y la competencia
National Commission of Markets and Competition

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Up-to-date Information on EC Regulatory: Key Resources

Transmission System Operators (TSO) and Distribution System Operator (DSO)

Transmission System Operators (TSOs) and Distribution System Operators (DSOs) are pivotal entities in the energy sector, ensuring the effective transmission and distribution of energy. On a European scale, the European Network of Transmission System Operators for Electricity (ENTSO-E) and Gas (ENTSO-G) provide overarching insights into energy infrastructure and market dynamics. They can be especially informative for those interested in Energy Communities.

Provides insights into energy infrastructure and electricity market developments across Europe.
[ENTSO-E Official Site](#)
[ENTSO-E List of Members](#)

Offers insights into gas infrastructure and market trends throughout Europe.
[ENTSO-G Official Site](#)
[ENTSO-G Members](#)

LIFE-BECKON [LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform – Guidance Hub](#)

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Up-to-date Information on EC Regulatory: Key Resources

Energy Agencies

The European Energy Network (EnR)
A voluntary collaboration of European energy agencies.
[European Energy Network Official Site](#)

European Federation of Agencies and Regions for Energy and Environment (FEDARENE)
FEDARENE is a leading European network of regional and local organizations dedicated to implementing, coordinating, and facilitating energy and environmental policies.
[FEDARENE Official Site](#)

Examples from LIFE-BECKON demo sites:

Агенция за устойчиво енергийно развитие
Sustainable Energy Development Agency

Energistyrelsen
Danish Energy Agency

Instituto para la Diversificación y Ahorro de la Energía
Institute for the Diversification and Saving of Energy

 [LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform – Guidance Hub](#)

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Video 6: Financing of Energy Communities and Public Aids

Financing of Energy Communities and Public Aids

29 January 2024

LIFE-BECKON

Co-funded by the European Union

Introduction

2

Energy Communities are becoming more and more popular, since they provide one solution for the progress of smart energy transition.

In this Capacity Building Module, we **define Energy Communities**, by delving into the **roles played by various authority levels** in providing financial support and public aids, as well as into the **diverse forms of funding** available to Energy Communities.

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For who?

Videos are targeted to any stakeholder interested in Energy Communities:

- **Municipalities** supporting the creation of Energy Communities
- **Ministries** and **Public authorities** at local, regional and national levels
- **Energy agencies** and **Energy companies**
- **Local associations**
- **Investors** and **Renewable energy developers**
- **Consultants**
- **Citizens**

4

Public aids

5

Public aids from different authority levels

To stimulate **growth** and encourage **community participation**, different kinds of public aids play a significant role.

Public aids for Energy Communities can be **organized on multiple levels**:

- **Ministries and Authorities** have the role of:
 - Establishing **favorable regulatory frameworks**.
 - Coordinating **regional and national efforts**.
 - **Monitoring and evaluating progress**.
- **Municipalities** have the role of:
 - Building up **technical assistance and capacity-building**, such as workshops, courses, and mentorship programs.
 - Helping to facilitate **partnerships and networks**.
 - Local energy **planning and policy support**.
 - **Partnering with local stakeholders** for project development.
 - Providing **public spaces for renewable installations**.

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Role of Municipalities

Municipal support mechanisms can be classified into two distinct types:

- **Direct support mechanisms**
 - Joint investments
 - Jointly managed energy utilities
 - Collaborative infrastructure investments
 - Opportunities for leasing energy from rural Energy Communities
- **Indirect support mechanisms**
 - Legal and policy frameworks
 - Provision of finances and resources
 - Promotion of community engagement

i [Rural Energy Community Hub Guide: Empowering Municipalities to Develop and Support Rural Energy Communities](#)

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Role of Municipalities

Municipalities can also take on **additional roles**, including:

- **Initiating** - by establishing new Energy Communities.
- **Creating favorable conditions** - by setting the stage for Energy Communities to establish themselves.
- **Working in partnership** - by collaborating with existing Energy Communities.
- **Participating** - by being consumers in the Energy Community.

i [mPower GUIDE 2: Building Energy Communities](#)

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Technical Assistance Office (TAO)

In the Life Beckon project, Technical Assistance Offices have been created to support the setup and implementation of Energy Communities.

These offices are planned to be transformed into permanent services, fostering the active role of municipalities in the energy transition in Bulgaria, Denmark, and Spain.

Technical Assistance Offices utilize the existing network of Energy offices in each country to support potential Energy Communities across municipalities.

i [LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform](#)

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Example of Municipal support for Energy Community in Ferla, Italy

In the small village of Ferla, Sicily, with a population of around 2,000, the mayor's vision of change through small actions has become a reality. The municipality, driven by a dedicated energy policy councilor, established trust with citizens through sustainability initiatives, like creating the first "compost village" and achieving a 75% waste collection rate.

Previous investments in PV plants, funded by PO FERS 2007/2013 and POI Energia 2015/16, resulted in 311 kW production, saving €90,000 and adding €30,000 to the municipal budget from the [GSE](#).

In 2021, the municipality collaborated with the University of Catania on a 20 kW PV system, showcasing a successful community energy project. The partnership with the university exemplified a "best practice," translating academic goals into tangible local benefits.

While maintaining authority, the municipality actively involved the community, opening a call for citizens and SMEs to join "Common Light." This inclusive approach, meeting legal requirements, makes Ferla's initiative a compelling example of a Community Energy Cooperative (CEC).

Ferla's success has attracted interest from neighboring municipalities, seeking guidance on replicating this balanced and inclusive energy transition strategy. Buoyed by achievements, Ferla plans to expand renewable energy technologies, including increased production power and exploring advanced storage systems.

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Forms of funding

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Financing

Financing is one of the **most significant challenges** that Energy Communities face. Overcoming financial barriers requires a **mix of innovative approaches and existing instruments**.

Financial aids for Energy Communities are **primarily at the national level**. Possible sources for aid and types of applications **vary in different countries and regions**. Energy Communities are **often financed by citizens**, and many **engage in crowdfunding to raise money directly from their community**.

More advanced Energy Communities sometimes also use **bank loans**. Access to financing through bank loans is **not always easy**, as they require **guarantees**.

[EUCENA Best Practice Guide for Southeast Europe](#)

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Public Aids by financial subsidies

One of the key public aids to stimulate growth within Energy Communities is **financial subsidies**.

There are various forms, including:

- **Self-financing**
- **Subsidies and grants**
- **Bank Financing**
- **Crowdfunding**
- **Crowdlending**
- **Financial Lease**
- **Alternative Financing**
- **Local authority or municipal support**
- **Cooperative fund**

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Forms of financial subsidies

Self-financing

Self-financing involves funding energy projects through the active participation of community members as both investors and decision-makers. For self-financing to thrive, a project must be financially viable, appealing, and instill trust among the community members.

Subsidies and grants

There are many subsidies at local, national and European level to promote energy efficiency improvement activities of houses and renewable energy projects. Public calls for NextGeneration European funds are open regularly in each Member State. There are many programmes regarding renewable Energy Communities. There is some digital platforms that work as subsidy browsers, including:

- [EU Financial Assistance-website](#)
- [Funding & Tender-Portal](#)
- [EuroVienna](#)
- [Welcome Europe](#)
- [Eucalls](#)
- [Finance4hope](#)

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Forms of financial subsidies

Bank financing

Bank financing might be difficult to obtain. It usually provides up to 80% of the funds, with the remaining 20% supplied by other means. Alternative to traditional bank loans may be in case of Energy Communities:

- **Ethical loans** - There exist banking institutions that operate as banks or cooperatives of financing services only for those projects, taking care of the **social and environmental impact as much as the economic benefits**.
- **Green loans** -There are many green loans available from diverse financial institutions. An example of green loans is the European Investment Bank (hereinafter, "EIB"). This green loan is a **private financing instrument** for energy efficiency ("PF4EE"). Its main goal is to **raise the private financing of energy efficiency improvement projects**.
- **Social loans** - This assistance is designated for initiatives aimed at **aiding individuals who are under the poverty threshold, underserved populations**, those with **disabilities**, as well as **migrants and individuals** who have been uprooted from their homes.

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Forms of financial subsidies

Bank financing

- **Sustainability-linked loans** - Interest rates vary **depending on the borrower's adherence** to and realization of set sustainability targets, known as Key Performance Indicators (KPIs), with rates adjusting according to whether these obligations are satisfied or not.
- **Credit sections** - **Intermediation services** that cooperatives offer apart from their main activity through an entity without self-legal status and **limit the active and passive operations the cooperative and its partners can do**.
- **Loans for homeowners' associations** - Bank Institutions offer **loans for works, installations, etc.** for homeowners' associations to allow them to finance their projects. Some of them are **focused on reaching an energy efficiency improvement**.
- **Loan Guarantee** - The provision of a loan guarantee is particularly common for REC projects. This financing source consists of a **third party who guarantees the payment** in case the project is unable to meet its debt obligations.

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Forms of financial subsidies

Crowdfunding

Crowdfunding is a **decentralized financing source** which allows **offering funds to little enterprises through online platforms**. They became regulated by Regulation (EU) 2020/1503. This regulation establishes **some limits in the project financing**.

It usually consists of **specialized platforms** which facilitate transactions between the promoters of the project and investors. Crowdfunding has many modalities, including:

- **Reward-based crowdfunding** - The project owner describes its project on a platform and in return of donations the owners provide rewards to the donators.
- **Investment crowdfunding** - In this type of crowdfunding that is also well known as equity crowdfunding, the investors will invest on a project, but they will agree a return with the project owner in case the project makes profit.

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Forms of financial subsidies

Crowdfunding

- **Donation crowdfunding** - It is often used in case of **non -profitable causes**, such as natural disasters, wars, etc. It is based on **people donating their money** and it is common to **organize a draw between funders**.
- **Profit-sharing/Revenue-sharing** - The community project can share **future profits or revenues with the crowd in return for funding now**.
- **Hybrid models** - Offer businesses the opportunity to **combine elements of more than one crowdfunding type**.

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Forms of financial subsidies

Crowdfunding

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Forms of financial subsidies

Crowdfunding

Crowdfunding operates through **online platforms to engage a broad audience**, and there are numerous platforms available. To select the most suitable one, remember to consider:

- **Platform Specifics** - Some platforms specialize in **particular types of projects**.
- **Popularity at the Scale Needed** - It is crucial to choose platforms with a **high number of users** within the desired **geographical scope of the project**, whether it's regional, national, or European.
- **Fees and Remuneration Schemes** - Always be mindful of the **platform's fees** (commonly fixed or commission-based) and understand any **capital limits** they may impose.
- **National Rules and Regulations** – Be **aware of regulations** is essential, as many member states have implemented strict rules to protect private investors.
- **Headquarters** - Consider **where the money is transferred and stored** by the platform to ensure its safety.
- **Features** - Evaluate the various features offered by the platform to determine its **suitability for running a successful fundraising campaign**.

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Forms of financial subsidies

Crowdlending

Crowdlending is a form of private financing conducted between companies based on mutually agreed conditions. Various platforms facilitate this type of financing, with examples including [Ecrowd](#).

Ecrowd serves as a platform that **connects companies with investors**. Notably, it operates **without the involvement of banks or intermediaries**. Instead, Ecrowd's role is to **promote companies and investors**, facilitating their connection through specialized browsers.

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Forms of financial subsidies

Financial lease

There are various types of financial lease, including:

- **Leasing** - It is a financial lease in which the person who needs certain assets cannot or does not want to acquire them directly to not risk its capital. In exchange, the financial institution receives recurrent payments until a certain date. Having reached that date, the person can decide to renew the contract or acquire the asset through a purchase option.
- **Renting** - The difference between renting and leasing is that renting does not necessarily include the purchase option.
- **Purchase in instalments** - This is an agreement in which the Buyer does not pay full price the moment they get the asset. The buyer pays certain instalments through certain periods of time.

Important to note that Leasing or Renting renewable energy projects may not be possible, since European Law requires Renewable Energy Communities to own them.

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Forms of financial subsidies

Alternative funding

There are also alternative forms of funding, including:

- **Collective installation purchase** - People who live in a **certain geographical area** are interested in acquiring certain generation facilities so they **commit to join efforts and capital** between them to find the company which can offer best conditions to acquire the asset.
- **Selling self-consumption surpluses** – This type concerns Renewable Energy Community (REC). With this form of funding, it is possible to sell the self-consumption surpluses to the grid to **partially finance the generation facilities** that a REC could hold. Its feasibility and potential would depend on whether the Member State in which the generation facility is established, allows the sale of the surpluses to their own electric system and subject to which conditions.
- **Fees to the Energy Community**- Monthly or annual fees paid by the Energy Community users might also be considered as a funding resource for the community.

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Forms of financial subsidies

Local authority or municipal support

Local and regional authorities can offer financial support, including **initial seed funding or access to revolving funds**. Additionally, they can provide **valuable guidance on financial planning** and assist in **infrastructure investment**.

Subsidies and grants

A cooperative revolving fund is established to provide **funding for a designated purpose**, utilizing the **generated income from investments** to support the same objective. When a fund is seeking new projects to invest in, it presents an **opportunity for fledgling renewable energy projects** to receive support at their initial stages.

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Real-life examples

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Support Schemes in Italy

Incentives connected to network tariffs based on a Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA)

According to article 42-bis of the Law 8/2020, a premium tariff is envisaged to support energy sharing and storage. This premium tariff will be paid by [GSE](#). Facilities with a capacity of less than 1 MW that are either owned by REC or part of a CSC (Collective Self-Consumption) operation qualify for this incentive. Consumers receive this special rate exclusively for the portion of energy that is produced and used at the same time (on an hourly basis) within the same primary grid station operating at medium voltage.

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Support Schemes in Italy

Tools to access finance

The Ministry offers guidance on securing financial support. Article 14 of Legislative Decree 199 lays out the coordination framework among the initiatives launched by the National Recovery and Resilience Plan (PNRR) and the mechanisms for sector-specific incentives. Specifically, paragraph e) details that, in the execution of Mission 2, Component 2, Investment 1.2 "Promotion of renewables for community's energy and self-consumption" it outlines the criteria and procedures for providing financing at zero interest covering up to 100% of the admissible expenses for the growth of the energy community, as outlined in Article 31. This support is aimed at smaller municipalities for establishing renewable energy production facilities, potentially in conjunction with energy storage systems.

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Support Schemes in Denmark

Under BEK no 1162 of 09/08/2022, DKK 4 million have been set aside from 2022 to 2025 to finance these subsidies in order on subsidies for local Energy Communities and local anchoring. Renewable energy actors can apply for individual grants for local Energy Communities and local anchoring or climate strategies at the Danish Energy Agency “Energisylselsens” website. Smaller projects, aimed at providing information, and larger programmes can be funded under this programme.

BEK no 1069 article 16 imposes an obligation on those suppliers to calculate the tariffs for REC and CEC on the basis of the assessment by those electricity supply companies of the benefits resulting from the REC and CEC use of the energy grid.

The municipality of Copenhagen offers the programme Solar Pool, which subsidises up to 50% of the consulting expenses resulting from support from a professional technical advisor to carry out an initial screening on a property to determine whether it is suitable for a solar panel installation. The subsidy is also capped at DKK 15.000, including VAT (approximately 2000€). This subsidy is available to the owners of privately owned multi-story residential properties with a minimum of five housing units located in Copenhagen, property administrators or advisors representing property owners or private business enterprises.

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Hyperion, Greece

Hyperion is a **not-for-profit Energy Community** based in Athens, Greece. Main motivation is to create a **viable and replicable model of collective self-consumption**.

Hyperion is funded through **member equity participation, donations, and a crowdfunding campaign**, so as to provide low-interest micro-loans.

The crowdfunding is organized by Hyperion through **Genervest crowd-investment platform**. This platform was chosen for its **capacity to facilitate micro and medium-sized investments in renewable energy projects with social impact**. The crowdfunding is coordinated by Genervest and Greenpeace Greece for **effective media outreach**.

Tips for crowdfunding?

Emphasize the **need for a narrative addressing current events** like the energy crisis, while also tackling **broader issues** such as climate change and energy poverty. Successful crowdfunding campaigns should **resonate with various audience segments by addressing multiple relevant points**.

[EUCENA Best Practice Guide for Southeast Europe](#) [Genervest](#)

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Solar In Kutë, Albania

Kutë community has been actively involved in the successful fight against the Poçem hydropower project on the Vjosa river. Together with EcoAlbania Kutë, as the country’s first solar village, has become a **milestone project for sustainable development in Albania**. The project was implemented by EcoAlbania, RiverWatch and Euronatur.

This project got **financial support from the Swiss Embassy in Albania**. **Donations from citizens** we also collected through **crowdfunding**. The crowdfunding platform used for this project was GoFundMe, while the crowdfunding was boosted by Patagonia and Euronatur.

[EUCENA Best Practice Guide for Southeast Europe](#) [GoFundMe](#)

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Do you want to explore in depth EU public funds?

You can use RESCoop Financing tracker. This monitoring tool evaluates the extent to which EU public financial resources, such as the Recovery & Resilience, Cohesion, and Modernisation Funds, are utilized by member countries to aid Energy Communities.

[RESCoop - Financing tracker](#)

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Video 7: Technical and technological considerations for Energy Communities

Technical and technological considerations for Energy Communities

29 January 2024

Co-funded by the European Union

Introduction

2

Energy Communities are becoming more and more popular, since they provide one solution for the progress of smart energy transition.

In this Capacity Building Module, a wide range of technical and technological considerations when operating Energy Communities are presented, along with **examples of different solutions/technologies** that can be used in an Energy Community setting.

For who?

Videos are targeted to any stakeholder interested in Energy Communities:

- **Municipalities** supporting the creation of Energy Communities
- **Ministries and Public authorities** at local, regional and national levels
- **Energy agencies and Energy companies**
- **Local associations**
- **Investors and Renewable energy developers**
- **Consultants**
- **Citizens**

4

Technical issues of Energy Communities

Energy Communities are organizations (legal entities) that can perform different activities of energy value chain.

These include *generation, distribution, storage, retail, sustainable mobility*, etc. The most common generation activity in Energy Communities is **photovoltaic generation for collective self consumption**. Many other technologies also exist, but photovoltaics have many advantages that make them popular in distributed small-scale production.

In this Capacity Building Module, we mostly focus on technical and technological considerations that have to be taken into account for PV systems for collective self-consumption.

Technical and technological considerations for Energy Communities

Technical and technological complexities

In smart energy transition, societies transform **from concentrated to distributed energy production**. Utilization of fossil fuels is drastically decreased, and renewable energy sources are utilized instead.

The role of **energy storage** is also becoming more important, since **more flexibility is required** due to **growing share of varying weather-dependent production** - wind and solar.

Energy Communities are **one solution in enabling smart energy transition**. However, some technical and technological considerations are inevitably crucial, including:

- The need for **new equipment** for the **electrification of the Energy Communities and transport**, on top of the needs for **devices for local energy production and storage**.
- The need to have an **overall control system upon the sources and consumption targets** of the Energy Communities.
- The need to **continuously and properly maintain all the devices** used in the Energy Communities.

i [LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform – Guidance Hub](#)

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Technical and technological complexities

The most common goals of setting up an Energy Community are **to promote renewable energy**, **to reduce citizen's energy consumption**, and **to lower their energy bills**.

Energy Communities can cover **various parts of the energy value chain**, including **production, distribution, supply, consumption, and aggregation**. To be able to carry out such actions, **different technical devices are necessarily required**. Also, a greater variety of actions results in **more complicated technical system** requiring more and more attention and service.

For example, if one member* of the Energy Community produces **excess energy at a certain instant of time**, this can **be sold to other members, stored in electric or thermal storage, or supplied to power grid**.

To be able to **operate reliably**, both the hardware and software of an Energy Community require **constant maintenance**. **More complicated the system, more maintenance and service is called for**.

i [Energy Communities to transform the EU's energy system](#)

*The members of an Energy Community, beyond the traditional role of **consumers**, they can also become **prosumers**, as they can **both consume and produce energy**.

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Common considerations for Energy Communities

The **frequency** with which any considerations or issues arise in Energy Communities highly depends on the **complexity of its energy system**:

- **Simple systems** result in **high degree of reliability**.
- **PV systems** are most typically utilized. They are **very reliable**, with **minor need for service**.
- When the energy system gets **more complicated**, the need of service increases.
 - *For example, small-scale wind turbines require regular technical service.*

Common technical/technological considerations for Energy Communities include:

- Required **firmware and software updates** of the energy system - those can be carried out by active members.
- **Adjustments of the control system to optimize the operation** - those can be usually carried out by active members.
- **Blowout of electric fuses or other electric protective devices** - this can be usually fixed by active members.
- **More specific technical problems in devices** – these may include problems of PV inverter or battery management system of energy storage. Some of these issues may be solved by active members, but often professional service is required.

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Technical checklist for solar power installations

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Technical checklist for solar power installations

Energy Communities often utilize solar power systems. In this Module, we present technical checklist for PV installations.

- ✓ **Obtain necessary permits:** Contact your local authorities or building authorities to inquire about permits and regulations for PV installations.
- ✓ **Hire a professional installer:** Engage a reputable solar PV installer or energy consultant with experience in community-focused projects with experience in system design and installation.
- ✓ **System design:** Work with your installer to design the PV system based on your energy requirements, available space, and budget. Consider the placement on site of panels, inverters, wiring, and mounting structures.

 [LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform – Guidance Hub](#)

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Technical checklist for solar power installations

- ✓ **Financing and incentives:** Explore financing options and available incentives for community-based solar installations.
- ✓ **Installation:** Schedule the installation with your chosen installer. Ensure the site is prepared, including any necessary electrical upgrades and the availability of space.
- ✓ **Electrical inspection:** Arrange for an electrical inspection to ensure compliance with safety standards and local regulations.
- ✓ **Interconnection:** Coordinate with your utility company to establish a net metering agreement or other interconnection requirements. This allows excess electricity generated by your PV system to be fed back into the grid.

 [LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform – Guidance Hub](#)

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Technical checklist for solar power installations

- ✓ **Metering and monitoring:** Install a bi-directional meter or a monitoring system to track the energy generated by your PV system and the electricity consumed from the grid. Enable community members to access and monitor their individual and collective energy data, fostering awareness and engagement.
- ✓ **Final inspections and approvals:** Schedule any final inspections required by local authorities or utility companies. Obtain all necessary approvals and certifications for the operation of your PV system.
- ✓ **System activation:** Once all inspections and approvals are obtained, your PV system can be activated. Test the system to ensure it is functioning properly and producing electricity as expected.

[LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform – Guidance Hub](#)

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Operation and maintenance of solar power systems

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Operation and maintenance of solar power systems

Solar power systems are generally **very reliable**, but to ensure **high-quality operation for a longer period**, **technical knowledge** is always required.

In Energy communities, the role of **Operations Manager/Coordinator** is crucial. This person is responsible for:

- Overseeing the **day-to-day operation** of the solar energy system.
- Ensuring **optimal functioning and meeting of performance targets**.
- **Coordinating maintenance and repairs** as needed.
- **Monitoring energy production and consumption** patterns.
- **Implementing protocols for shutdown, start-up, and troubleshooting**.

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[LIFE-BECKON OSS Platform – Guidance Hub](#)

Preventive maintenance of solar power systems

Reliable operation of solar power system calls for preventive maintenance schedule. Preventing maintenance tasks may include:

- **Regular cleaning of the solar panels** to remove dirt, debris, and shading objects. Inspect for **physical damage** as well, such as cracks or corrosion.
- Check the **inverters** for **connections**, and **monitor performance**, and inspect for any **signs of faults or malfunctions**. Follow the **manufacturer’s recommendations for firmware updates or component replacements** if necessary.
- Monitor the variables that determine the **health of the batteries**. Follow the **manufacturer’s instructions for maintenance**.
- Determine the **frequency** at which each maintenance task should be performed based on the **manufacturer’s recommendations and system-specific factors**.
- Consider **environmental factors**, such as the level of dust, pollution, or extreme weather conditions that **may impact maintenance requirements**.

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Preventive maintenance of solar power systems

Preventive maintenance tasks should also be **scheduled on a regular basis**, to make sure they are taken care off on time, without compromising the function of the system.

Maintenance task	Frequency
Solar panel cleaning	Annually
Inverter inspection	Semi-annually
Firmware updates	As recommended

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Examples

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Diversity of technical options in Energy Communities

Many Energy Communities utilize **solar power**, but there are also cases of Energy Communities that rely on **other renewable energy sources**.

Because the diversity of technical solutions in Energy Communities is high, **general instructions of Energy Communities' technical options cannot be given**.

Instead, in this section we give examples of **different technical options that have been implemented in different real-life cases of Energy Communities**.

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Use of existing grids and meters in Energy Community

Implementation of new EU Energy Directives will give rise to **new rules dealing with the exchange of electricity locally**, and how to **make it easier for electricity customers to take part in the market through flexible consumption and production**.

As Energy Communities become more and more common, it is also necessary to clarify how local existing distribution networks and meters are part of the Energy Communities.

There are several different options for utilizing existing grids and meters, and national legislations vary.

[Handbook for Energy Communities](#)

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Solar PV connected to local consumption

One typical form of Energy Community is to **utilize solar electricity in block of flats**.

Then, solar electricity system is typically installed on the roof of the building. Produced power can be used in the building/Energy Community or supplied to the grid.

It is worth noting that local rules and restrictions may affect the system.

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Local PV production and storage for flexibility

Local utilization of solar electricity can be enhanced by means of an energy storage. Heat energy storage can also be used to **provide flexibility**, but if the aim is to **shift the consumption of solar electric energy to evening time, battery energy storages need to be utilized.**

During daytime, local PV production exceeds consumption, and the excess of energy is stored.

By utilizing stored energy during evening, the use of expensive grid electricity can be avoided.

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Heat pumps with local energy sources

Electrification of societies is a key factor in smart energy transition. The goal is to **produce a growing share of energy (electricity and heat) without burning.**

Direct electric heating is one option, but the efficiency of heating can be significantly increased by utilizing heat pumps.

A heat pump exploits heat from different sources (air, water, soil, roof) for space heating and domestic hot water production.

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Buffer heat tanks for smoothing peak loads

Heat storages can have several roles in smart energy transition. These may include:

- Store excess electricity in case of surplus of weather-dependent production.
- Offer flexibility for power grid by means of controllable consumption.
- Offer heat energy for consumption.
- Offer flexibility for district heating network.

Polar Night Energy

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Electric vehicles and use of batteries for flexibility

Due to the **green transition**, more and more **electric cars** will be connected to power grid during the next few years. This will have several **consequences**. These may include:

- Consumption of electric energy will increase. Smart charging would need to be carried out in Energy Communities in order to enable sufficient power for simultaneous charging of several vehicles.
- Battery energy storages of electric vehicles can be used for energy needs and energy optimization of buildings and Energy Communities, if V2G (vehicle-to-grid) is enabled.
- Commercial high-power charging stations of electric vehicles may cause challenges to grid balance.

Combined cooling and heat recovery

In many countries, **significant amount of cooling power is required most of the year**. Targets of cooling are for example **indoor air, groceries and other products requiring lower temperatures**.

In cooling applications, thermal energy is transferred from one place to another. Consequently, if one location is cooled, another location will be heated.

If heat loss of cooling is utilized, then the total efficiency of cooling (e.g., in Energy Communities) will be

Examples of heat loss targets are local heat storage, indoor air and district heating network.

Solar heat added to heating system

An Energy Community can produce part of its heat demand, for example, using **solar heating collectors** which use **solar power to produce heat for space heating and domestic hot water**.

The installation can be integrated in the building or district level together with an additional heat source (e.g., district heating) to ensure that the heat demand is always covered.

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Video 8: Operation of Energy Communities

Operation of Energy Communities

29 January 2024

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Introduction

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Energy Communities are becoming more and more popular, since they provide one solution for the progress of smart energy transition.

In this Capacity Building Module, our focus is on the **operational phase of Energy Communities**. We provide resources and tips for effective **monitoring and evaluation**. Furthermore, we explore the intricate aspects of **maintenance**, considering the **diverse forms** it can take within the context of Energy Communities.

For who?

Videos are targeted to any stakeholder interested in Energy Communities:

- **Municipalities** supporting the creation of Energy Communities
- **Ministries and Public authorities** at local, regional and national levels
- **Energy agencies and Energy companies**
- **Local associations**
- **Investors and Renewable energy developers**
- **Consultants**
- **Citizens**

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Operation phase of Energy Communities

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Phases of setting up Energy Communities: Operation

In this Module we will concentrate on **Operation phase** of an Energy Community.

When an Energy Community is **fully operational**, the focus shifts to **maintaining and improving the activities** of the Energy Community. The community members work together to ensure the project **runs smoothly**, and they continue to **monitor and evaluate its performance**. They also **explore new opportunities for growth and expansion**, ensuring that the Energy Community remains relevant and effective in its mission to create a more sustainable future.

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Actions of Energy Community operation

When an Energy Community is in operation, **constant maintenance work** is required to ensure its reliable operation, to prepare for the future, and to support other projects.

In addition to technical maintenance and control of Energy Community, also **governance related issues** need to be taken care of all the time. Remember, it is important to:

- **Prepare for the future**, prepare for changes.
- **Prepare for technical problems** that might occur.
- Support other Energy Community projects and **spread the knowledge** about them.
- **Improve control** - optimize energy management and prepare for future changes.
- **Set maintenance programme** - it is important that maintenance is carried out on a regular basis.
- **Develop new projects** - development of an Energy Community is a continuous process.

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Materials of Energy Communities to be included in operation phase

LIFE-BECKON mainly concentrates on **collective self-consumption**, but in general Energy Community in operation phase needs to have **several aspects (and corresponding documentation) included**.

Legal entity related:

- Documents for regular actions.
- Financial balance sheet for income and expenditures.
- Quality control checklist and standards for the operation of Energy Community.
- Maintenance and evaluation support for operation, objectively verifiable indicators.

Technical assistance related:

- Operation and maintenance instructions.
- Balance sheet for generation and consumption of energy.
- Monitoring of self-production (**e.g., PV**) installation.

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Monitoring and evaluation of Energy Communities

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Monitoring and evaluation of Energy Communities

One option for **monitoring and evaluation (M&E) tool** of Energy Communities is logical framework (**Logframe**) approach.

- A Logical Framework is a **matrix** in which overall objective, purpose, expected results and activities, assumptions, objectively verifiable indicators and sources of verification are represented for an Energy Community.
- The **Logical Framework Matrix (LFM)** facilitates planning, execution, and evaluation of a development intervention, and is therefore present and used in different phases of the cycle of operations.
- It is presented in the **form of a table** summarising the key elements of a Project/Programme, which is used as a **management tool**, to improve the design of Interventions, and for monitoring and reporting purposes during implementation.

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Types of maintenance of Energy Communities

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Maintenance

The **maintenance of an Energy Community** is a comprehensive concept that can be divided into several subtitles.

[Rural Energy Community Advisory Hub](#)

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Community maintenance

In **community maintenance**, following matters need to be taken into account:

- The **management of rural Energy Communities** is important. This means that management of financial, operational and project related issues needs to be taken care of.
- **Diversity of community** members needs to be attained and preserved.
- **Regular dialogue** with members and residents living around energy installations needs to be held.
- **Shared vision and rules for decision making** to reflect more ambitious goals and objectives needs to be revised.
- **New projects** need to be explored and **new members** need to be recruited.

[Rural Energy Community Advisory Hub](#)

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Staff maintenance

Commitment and competence of key persons of operational Energy Communities need to be constantly evaluated and taken care of.

- **Ensure diversity** of key personnel who are highly committed.
- **Include entrepreneurial skill sets** in the leadership team.
- Find out the main factors affecting the level of **staff commitment**.

[Rural Energy Community Advisory Hub](#)

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Financial maintenance

It is very important that the operation of Energy Community is **financially viable**.

- **Regular operations** need to be maintained and **revenue streams** need to be ensured and monitored.
- Technical equipment of setting up an Energy Community requires investments. Highly important is that **the return of investment (ROI) is taken care of**.
- **Careful financial maintenance** is one important factor that helps in **creating trust** and making community members **more and more engaged**.

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Support maintenance

Support for Energy Community needs to be maintained and strengthened.

- One way of strengthening the support is to **pursue membership in larger community energy networks**.
- **Energy policy has a huge impact!** Thus, utilize advocates through political connections.
- **Publicity is important.** Although your Energy Community would be operational and financially viable, majority of people may not be aware of its benefits. **Wider knowledge supports the support!**

[Rural Energy Community Advisory Hub](#)

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Technical maintenance

Technical maintenance creates a foundation for reliable operation.

- Wide range of services has to be provided. This increases flexible operation and reliability. **Staff needs to have ability to carry out basic maintenance.**
- **Invest in monitoring!** Fault situations and interruptions of operation can often be avoided by the combination of monitoring and technical competence of staff.
- **Keep record of the growth in energy production and consumption.** This is important from monitoring point of view, but it can also help to engage members.
- Careful technical maintenance results in achieving **CO₂ emission reductions**.

[Rural Energy Community Advisory Hub](#)

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Network maintenance

Network around an Energy Community requires continuous maintenance and enlargement.

- Try to **achieve recognition** also outside the Energy Community.
- **Continuously grow** and reach out to more households and organisations, both locally and regionally.
- **Enlarge your network** by replicating successful projects to other contexts.
- Improve current processes to **enhance benefits for all parties involved**.
- Utilize **intermediary organisations** to share knowledge and enable other communities to improve or set up a rural Energy Community.
- Contribute towards transformative change in the energy sector. For example, take ownership of the grid through being the **Distribution System Operator (DSO)**.

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Need inspiration and practices from other European initiatives?

As Energy Community Platform provides resources, the main added value of LIFE Beckon is to help interested stakeholders to understand how to create Energy Community step-by-step.

By choosing Operation in Energy Community Platform, updating resources of many Energy Community projects in operation phase become available.

[Energy Community Platform](#)

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